

EXPLORING NON-MEDICAL APPROACHES TO MENTAL HEALTH FOR ROMANI COMMUNITIES IN EUROPE

Manuel García-Ramírez, Belén Soto-Ponce and Daniela E. Miranda

Center of Community Research and Action
Universidad de Sevilla
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Cover image: Net Menders in Valencia. Joaquín Sorolla, 1909

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About CESPYPD

The Coalition for the Study of Health, Power and Diversity (CESPYD) is the Center of Community Research and Action at the Universidad de Sevilla (US). The mission of CESPYPD is to increase the power, health and well-being of vulnerable groups and ethnic minorities such as low-income migrants, refugees and Romani populations. Our methodologies are based on stakeholder collaborations, synergies between disciplines, effective communication and utilization of available resources. We have developed a consolidated multi-level network to ensure the transformation of public health policies driven by the communities' priorities.

Dr. Manuel García-Ramírez (magarcia@us.es). Lead researcher and Project Coordinator. Professor at the US Dept. Social Psychology and founder of CESPYPD. Since 2012 he has been the coordinator of the research line "Psychosocial processes, culture, diversity and citizenship" of the PhD Programme in Psychology. A Fellow of the Society for Community Research and Action (SCRA, 27th Division of the American Psychology Association), Member of the International Academy of Intercultural Research, invited expert of the European Platform for Roma inclusion by the European Commission to develop the white paper on Roma health and housing for the European Union. In the last ten years he actively led and participated in relevant research initiatives in the field of public health and vulnerable and ethnic minorities groups, funded by institutions such as the Spanish R+D programme, the International Organization for Migration, the Open Society Foundations, the European Commission's DG JUST and DG SANTE. As the lead researcher Manuel coordinated the development of the framework providing critical feedback to his team.

Belen Soto Ponce (bsponce@us.es). Researcher. Pre-Doctoral Research Fellow at the Social Psychology Department at the US and researcher at CESPYPD. She holds an MA International Migrations and health, and MA in Clinical and Health Psychology. She has worked at the Refugee Reception Center in Sevilla. Belen has been involved in a project organized by the International Organization for Migration as a consultant. Currently, she's working with Romani communities in the project RoMoMatteR (Empowering at-Risk Roma Girls' Mattering through Reproductive Justice), funded by the DG Justice of the European Union Commission and JITANAS, a project aimed at building gendering capacity for Roma community organizations, funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science. Belen led the literature review and contextualized consortiums research.

Daniela E. Miranda (danimiranda@us.es). Researcher. Doctoral Candidate in the Social Psychology Department at the US and researcher at CESPYPD for the past six years. Her research focuses on developing advocacy strategies to defend the health rights of Romani women at the local level. In 2016 she received a scholarship for the implementation of the International Organization for Migrations Equi-Health and a project funded by the Open Society Foundations Roma Initiatives Office (2016-2019). She is an active member of the Society for Community Research and Action and a member of the European Public Health Alliance Roma health task force. Currently she collaborates with the University of Illinois at Chicago and the University of Lancaster in building Romani sensitivity in public health initiatives. Daniela planned the methodological aspects in the creation of this document with the aim of ensuring the participation of all consortium members in the final consensus and analysis.

Executive Summary

EXPLORING NON-MEDICAL APPROACHES TO MENTAL HEALTH FOR ROMANI COMMUNITIES IN EUROPE

Context

In 2016 the Open Society Foundations alongside the World Health Organization and World Bank urged global development efforts to reframe mental health approaches. These institutions urged for a mental health approach that included a human rights-based perspective that was linked to just social conditions. The Open Society Foundations Public Health Program developed a call to build a consortium across Europe that would explore non-medical approaches to mental health with Romani communities and other ethnic racialized groups. The purpose of this document is to provide a human rights approach to Romani mental health (RMH) that includes the voices from mental health experts, Romani civil society, grassroots organizations and researchers from various countries.

This report is the result of work coordinated by the Center of Community Research and Action at the Universidad de Sevilla (CESPYD). The report is organized into the following chapters: (1) Does RMH matter?, (2) why do we need a human rights-based approach?, (3) How can we use the existing knowledge of RMH to strength a human rights-based approach?, and (4) Where do we go from here?

Does Romani Mental Health Matter?

In 2020 the European Commission updated the EU Roma strategic framework. This framework further developed a series of horizontal objectives to ensure equality and inclusion of Romani across areas of education, employment, housing and health (European Commission, 2020). The new model—once again—does not make explicit mental health and psychological well-being as strategic axes of Romani progress and inclusion, it represents an ideal scenario for advocating for and anchoring RMH at the crossroads of Romani prosperity.

Evidence suggest that Romani are at a higher risk of experiencing mental health distress compared to non-Romani populations. In this section we review the known evidence and political efforts to improve Romani health. Although there is a gap in the data, there are a series of physical and social determinants that influence mental distress and wellbeing that are well known. Furthermore, Romani mental health can be understood from a framework that considers political factors that affect the wellbeing of Roma and mental distress understood across the spectrum of systemic, community and individual level factors.

Why do we need a human rights-based approach?

In this section we will justify the political nature of RMH and provide the rationale as to why a human rights-based approach can help us understand RMH as dependent on the rights at the political, social and economic circumstances of individuals and communities. The violation of these rights is understood as the direct cause of Romani experiences of mental distress. In this approach, mental distress is understood as any disturbance of thought, emotion, behavior, and relationships with others that lead to suffering and functional impairment in one or more major life activities (The Lancet, 2018; World Health Organization, 2004). Three different and interdependent levels mediate this relationship, i.e., societal, relational and intrapersonal.

We provide an analytical framework that understand mental distress as: (1) structural discrimination, (2) exclusion from social spheres, and (3) transmitted trauma. If Romani people across Europe are excluded from political participation, live isolated and have difficulties accessing resources and most live in situations of poverty, we consider this a form of collective violence towards Romani people passed from one generation to the next. These issues have links to the wellbeing of Romani people.

From this analytical framework, we then identify that there are different strategies to promote mental health of Romani communities, by including (1) strategies that promote psycho-political empowerment, (2) expanding the networks of Romani communities and (3) a multi-level approach to address systemic nature of Romani wellbeing.

How can we use the existing knowledge of RMH to strengthen a human rights-based approach?

Through a collaborative methodology we identified the state of the art of RMH from a human rights-based analytical framework, that included the meaningful participation of key stakeholders from the consortium and other external experts. The consortium was comprised of organizations from Italy, Ukraine, Germany and Czech Republic—with varied backgrounds and professions, for example: researchers, medical professionals, grassroots leaders and health care professionals

We systemized the evidence and contextualized their findings within academia. Following the human rights-based approach to Roma mental health (RMH), mental distress is apparent through the experience of multiple social disadvantages caused by structural discrimination dynamics. This in turn effects Romani communities at the individual level manifested through transmitted and interiorized trauma. Protecting human rights promotes feelings of recognition and influence within Romani populations, enhancing mental wellbeing. Nevertheless, this can only be achieved through a process where Romani people firstly build on critical awareness and strengths, expand and build new social networks and lastly, through the development of transformative multilevel changes.

Where do we go from here?

In this section we provide a series of questions to further our discussion based on (1) consortia findings; (2) priorities from survey, (3) answers to open-ended survey questions; (4) guidelines provided from external experts and (5) the conversations held during a series of workshops between November and December 2020. The recommendations are based on the collaboration for policy, research and public debate. The information has been grouped into a series overarching questions which are: (1) how can we develop research approaches that are free of violence, (2) how can we adopt a community development and organizing approach, (3) how can we address discrimination at multiple levels, and (4) how can we expand our conceptualization of trauma towards a strength-based approach? In each of these sections we provide a practical example.

We conclude with a series of limitations in the development of this report and next steps. Our findings propose that Romani mental wellbeing has become an important issue that is hidden from policies and recommendations, research and interventions. In order to move forward policies, research and grassroots efforts should aim at advocating to include Romani wellbeing as a priority at the EU level, contextualize current efforts within the effects of the pandemic, promote the leadership of women and youth. We urge researchers to partner directly with Romani communities as (co)researchers, and for health professionals to include a biopsychosocial perspective in their work.

EXPLORING NON-MEDICAL APPROACHES TO MENTAL HEALTH FOR ROMANI COMMUNITIES IN EUROPE

Context

The purpose of this document is to provide a human rights approach to Romani mental health (RMH) that includes the voices from mental health experts, Romani civil society, grassroots organizations and researchers in various countries. The Council of Europe's definition of Roma as "Roma, Sinti, Kale and related groups in Europe, including Travellers and the Eastern groups (Dom and Lom), and covers the wide diversity of the groups concerned, including persons who identify themselves as Gypsies and Gitanos." (Council of Europe, 2012, p. 4). Following the consensus reached between the participants of this document and the communication issued by the European Parliament in 2020, we will utilize the term "Romani" that recognizes the diversity and heterogeneity of these communities. This paper provides the state-of-the-art in regard to Romani and ethnic mental health to lay the foundation for the OSF Public Health Program's strategic direction in subsequent discussion, research, and support in the field of RMH.

In 2005, Europe became politically aware of the extreme conditions of 12 million Romani citizens and carried out many efforts that intended to improve their quality of life and prosperity. The impact that these oppressive conditions have on their mental health has persistently been largely overlooked. The updated EU Roma strategic framework adopted in 2020 has developed a series of horizontal objectives (i.e., fight and prevent antigypsyism and discrimination, reduce poverty and social exclusion to close the socio-economic gap, promote participation through empowerment) to ensure equality and inclusion of Romani across areas of education, employment, housing and health (European Commission, 2020). Although this new model—once again—does not make explicit mental health and psychological well-being as strategic axes of Romani progress and inclusion, it represents an ideal scenario for advocating for and anchoring RMH at the crossroads of Romani prosperity.

As in other ethnic, racialized and mistreated groups, on the few occasions when Romani mental health was laid on the table, discussion is usually based on medical approaches, which focus on cognitive individual-level processes or neurological issues (Banner, 2013). According to this author, individual differences found when implementing these medical approaches prove that factors such as life events, social relationships and social, cultural and economic environments have on mental health, as well as how these factors are closely interrelated with neurological conditions. In fact, evidence suggests that chronic and persistent psychological stressors or traumatic events can produce neurological changes, including changes in the structure and functioning of the brain (Kolasa & Elbert, 2007). Nevertheless, chronic psychological stress conditions, such as marginalization, discrimination or stigma, are merely considered part of the solid foundation of the psychological suffering inflicted on the Romani population. Therefore, the biological vision of the medical approach is necessary to explain and understand RMH, though not sufficient. Moreover, adopting it in an isolated vacuum can become an alibi for ignoring the psychological, social and political factors that impact biological determinants.

The biopsychosocial perspective has been strongly proposed because it offers a holistic view of individuals' mental health. Adopting a biopsychosocial approach (Engel, 1977) allows us to understand that psychological wellbeing and mental health depends on multiple psychosocial factors

such as individual lifestyles, social and community networks, living and working conditions, and general socioeconomic, cultural, political and environmental conditions where communities live on (Dahlgren & Whitehead, 1991). This approach stresses the urgency to adopt a perspective that links the protection and promotion of RMH with the protection of and respect for their human rights. Following this logic, focus must stress non-medical fields usually ignored when talking about Romani communities, which at the same time will probably be the most relevant factors on their mental health. Eggerman & Panter-Brick (2010) proved that everyday stressors provoke suffering in communities with well-defined and strict cultural values. Moreover, intersections between everyday adversity and maintenance of cultural values within a context where structural inequalities are imperative, can lead to entrapment in these communities. In this document we will use the term mental distress defined as the cumulative experiences of coping with injustices that are determined by the social determinants of mental health (UNHRC, 2019).

Although this document highlights a non-medical approach to mental health, we adopt a pragmatic paradigm to the research process that includes mixed methods in knowledge production (Mertens, 2014). This implies that we recognize the contributions of the medical approach and existing scientific data while bringing to the forefront knowledge developed through reflexivity, and social experiences. A pragmatic paradigm is a political effort as it brings in the voices of Romani communities and is considered scientific evidence as well (Kauskuh & Walsh, 2019). In this paper we consider the existing scientific, medical research, the narratives of communities, the knowledge of multiple experts and collectively make sense of the underlying issues to define clear action points.

Between September and December 2020, the Center for Community Research and Action at the Universidad de Sevilla (CESPYD) developed an approach to build critical knowledge with a consortium from Italy, Ukraine, Germany and Czech Republic. The main objectives were to answer the following questions:

1. Does Romani Mental Health Matter? Justifying the political nature of RMH.
2. Why do we need a human rights-based approach? Mapping recent recommendations to move towards a human rights approach and build an analytical framework.
3. How can we use the existing knowledge of RMH to strengthen a human rights-based approach? Systemizing evidences and contextualize findings within academia.
4. Where do we go from here? Designing recommendations based on the collaboration for policy, research and public debate to consensus key concepts and priorities.

In the next section we will provide an overview of RMH, the foundations of our framework and the evidence found to support it. Then we will share the recent literature linking psychological wellbeing to Romani, ethnicity and contextualize the main findings from each consortium.

Does Romani Mental Health Matter?

The purpose of this section is to piece together the data that suggests that Romani communities are at risk for experiencing mental distress. The socio-political nature of mental health determinants excludes minority groups such as Romani from decision-making processes (Ottersen, 2014). This is deep-rooted in anti-Romani sentiment within institutions, policies, traumatizing marginalization and violence over generations. Research consistently shows that even the perceived threat of racist exposure results in mental distress and worse quality of life (Williams, 2017). According to EU Midi reports, Romani continue to experience high prevalence of discriminatory experiences, and that almost half of the general population feel uncomfortable having Romani neighbors (FRA, 2020). The anti-Romani discrimination is the driver of the poor living conditions and the lack of available resources as it displays multiple layers of issues that link to poor quality of life at the individual, community and systemic levels (Zaharieva, 2020).

Evidences also suggest that Romani are at a higher risk of experiencing mental health distress compared to non-Romani populations. Romani have higher rates of alcohol and drug consumption and anxiolytic prescription medicine, analgesics or antipyretics (La Parra Casado, 2009), a symptom of unrecognized mental distress. Furthermore, Romani experience worse overall self-perceived health—physical, emotional and social health—compared to non-Romani (Sandor et al. 2017; La Parra, Gil-Gonzalez & de la Torre, 2016). When taking into account the experience of intersecting identities, new layers of discrimination occur that lead to mental distress. For example, Romani women have reported an overall lower life satisfaction and experience higher rates of gender violence (European Commission, 2014; FRA, 2013; Milenković, 2018). According to the World Health Organization gender violence is a leading cause of mental distress for women, in which institutions have recognized the increased risk of gender violence (WHO, 2017; UNFPA, 2020). Romani people who also identify with other minority groups—for example LGBTQ community, religious or racialized groups—are at risk of experiencing mental distress, more vulnerability and invisibility due to the tensions created between feelings of shame, reconciliation and pride of these identities early in life and during the life course (Máté, 2015). The Romani identity has been built on dominant narratives that have shaped the wellbeing of Romani communities. For example, blaming Romani culture for their living situations and lack of inclusion which then determines the contextual factors in which they grow and live.

Furthermore, evaluation and research approaches used to assess RMH have reinforced existing narratives used to oppress and abandon Romani communities. The mainstream approach to mental health entails binary categories, established through the development of normative patterns to diagnose mental health challenges. These are usually based on major populations' mental health status, individual characteristics and social adjustment. This ethnocentric diagnosis and evaluation approaches homogenizes all population groups, leaving behind racialized communities such as Romani groups, which indeed, have always been considered as deviant from the normative patterns. Besides, using a “one size fits all” approach to mental health -focused on biological and individual characteristics and with no consideration of other social spheres' weight on mental health challenges- will only palliate the damages done by unjust social contexts. Responding to this situation, need-based approaches to solve problems have been led by outside experts and programs that force Romani communities to be dependent users of services that mitigate some damage (Kretzman & McKnight, 2005). Consequently, Romani are considered helpless and are forced to assume this position in society.

Mental health in the context of man-made exclusion and violence and complex trauma as a result are very often political and need to be addressed beyond the clinical setting in a social-political space. A

helper-victim mindset would perpetuate the conception of Romani as weak people. This reinforces the idea that they are incapable of contributing to the prosperity of our society.

Let us be aware that if we do not succeed in guaranteeing the dignity and mattering - the psychological and psychosocial value - of European Romani communities, their life projects will continue to be frustrated, their lives will continue to deteriorate and feelings of contempt for the Romani will continue to take hold. It is the perfect scenario in which irresponsible influencers find the ground to consolidate the anti-Romani message in the institutions and political discourse.

We must be conscientious in offering proposals based on their strengths, on their ability to take care of themselves, as well as on the contribution that Romani has made and continues to make to the intangible wealth of European societies.

Why Do We Need a Human Rights-Based Approach?

In this section we will provide the rationale as to why a human rights-based approach can help us understand RMH as dependent on the political, social and economic circumstances of individuals and communities. If Romani people across Europe are excluded from political participation, live isolated and have difficulties accessing resources and most live in situations of poverty, we consider this a form of collective violence towards Romani people passed from one generation to the next. The message of the Special Rapporteur of Human Rights Council is clear. “There can be no good mental health without human rights” (p. 3) (2020). Some studies shown that Romani are at a significantly higher feelings of hopelessness and lack of control of their lives (Toth et. al., 2018). This sense of control, or agency, is strongly linked to wellbeing as it is understood as having the freedom to choose, and the opportunities and resources to thrive (Welzel, 2010).

In 2016 the Open Society Foundations alongside the World Health Organization and World Bank urged global development efforts to reframe mental health approaches and should aim to build inclusive communities with the adequate resources (Klein, 2016). The Lancet Commission declared mental health as a global public good and rights-based approach while the UN General Assembly considered factors within social, psychosocial, political, economic and physical environments that “enables individuals and populations to live a life of dignity, with full enjoyment of their rights and the equitable pursuit of their potential” (Patel et al, 2018; UNHRC, 2019, p.1). For this, a human rights-based approach entails that people’s voices matter and their needs are met. In 2019, Open Society Foundations committed to adopting a human-rights based approach that recognized that one of the principal causes of mental distress is the violation of human rights and protecting human rights will ensure wellbeing, therefore, should be complimentary to the medical approach.

As it is represented in the Figure 1, freedom and equality in dignity and rights, including civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, with no distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion or social origin (United Nations, 1948, p.2) are considered central to the human rights-based approach to RMH. The violation of these rights is direct cause of Romani experiences of mental distress—understood as any disturbance of thought, emotion, behavior, and relationships with others that lead to suffering and functional impairment in one or more major life activities (The Lancet, 2018; World Health Organization, 2004). Three different and interdependent levels mediate this relationship, i.e., at societal, relational and intrapersonal.

Figure 1. Human rights-based analytical framework to Romani mental health.

At societal level, structural discrimination suffered by Romani communities turns into violent treatments and practices from institutions and major population towards Romani. It is usually concordant with antigypsyism, which is defined as “a historically constructed, persistent complex of customary racism against social groups identified under the stigma ‘gypsy’ or other related terms, and incorporates: (1) homogenizing and essentializing perception and description of these groups, (2) the attribution of specific deviant characteristics to them, and (3) discriminating social structures and violent practices that emerge against that background, which have a degrading and ostracizing effect and which reproduce structural disadvantages” (Alliance Against Antigypsyism, 2016). This is evidenced through barriers to access education, housing or healthcare, criminalization of self-employment initiatives or stigmatization and negative beliefs towards Romani people, which deeply deteriorates mental health outcomes.

Structural discrimination practices lead to the exclusion of Romani communities from all social spheres, being pushed to live in precarious conditions and preventing Romani communities from fully participating in social and decision-making processes or accessing better employment or educational opportunities. The cooption of certain cultural values and traditions for the structural discriminatory mechanisms described above contribute to social exclusion (Kende et al., 2020) and intensifies experiences of distress. An example of this is the increased deterioration of RMH among Romani women due to strict gender relationships and roles established among some communities.

These processes of structural discrimination and exclusion from social spheres lead the victims to self-blame, convincing them that they are inferior to the others and do not deserve to be treated like the rest of the population or with the same rights. This internalization of oppression—understood as psychological oppression—is exercised by individuals against themselves and against their equals, internalizing a contemptuous vision of him/herself without having the right to participate in the society or feeling deserving of resources for his/her wellbeing. This leads to increased difficulties in participating in social spheres, as a result of mistrust and hostility (Fanon, 1963; Martín-Baró, 1996), as well as increased feelings of worthlessness, low self-esteem or powerlessness, increasing mental distress experiences among Romani population. Since these circumstances of discrimination and persecution have been suffered by the Romani population for centuries and across generations, the internalized oppression damages Romani community for generations and should be seen as an intergenerational trauma.

A human rights-based approach of Romani mental health explains how Romani people have resisted over centuries the adversities of oppression and develop strengths and resources to cope with and overcome them (Watts & Serrano-García, 2003). Behaviors and niches of resistance confronting oppressive socio-political structures explain the resilient vulnerability that Romani have displayed for centuries and that are an intrinsic part of their heritage, culture and way of life (Kidron, Kotliar & Kirmayer, 2019). This represents the capacity of Romani to recover themselves according to their interests, values and needs. Therefore, Romani mental wellbeing should be understood as a state of well-being in which the individual can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to contribute to the community (WHO, 2004). This implies a self-construction process linked to their capacity to create meaning and sense, as well as reflecting and thinking of oneself and society as a whole, while maintaining one’s culture, which provides a symbolic system necessary to make sense of new encounters (Garcia-Ramirez et al., 2011).

The development of critical thinking is the first stage in the journey towards becoming politically active members of society (Miranda et al., 2020; Garcia-Ramirez et al., 2011; Paloma et al., 2010). This critical thinking leads individuals to *build strengths* and believe that conditions can change because they are not—by nature—as they appear in a specific historical context. At the interpersonal level, RMH is associated with new social ties, organizations and social networks that develop new social references, increase *capacities to respond* to injustice assuring the involvement of public

institutions as well, civil organizations and the overall society (Albar-Marín & Miranda, 2020). Finally, this process leads to involvement in *transformative multi-level changes* oriented to the construction of fair social contexts. This includes the meaningful influence of Romani towards change on civil, economic, cultural, political and other social processes, accessing new employment niches and opportunities as well as healthy housing opportunities, or identifying different role models to envision diverse futures for themselves (Miranda et al., 2020; Escobar-Ballesta et al., 2018; Garcia-Ramirez et al., 2011).

The human rights-based approach to Romani mental health proposed follows international institutions' recommendations. The Human Rights Council from the United Nations highlights the must to overcome the different forms of intersectional discrimination such as "*stigma, prejudice, violence, abuse, social exclusion and segregation, illicit or arbitrary institutionalization, overmedicalization and treatment practices that do not respect their autonomy*" (UNHRC, 2017). Similarly, other institutions emphasize the need to allocate resources to prevent psychological difficulties, with special attention to the social determinants of health, such as inequalities, discrimination and violence suffered mostly by vulnerable groups such as the Romani. In addition, they highlight the need to strengthen awareness and commitment of society and governance for mental health (Council of Europe, 2019; UNHRC, 2019; Patel et al., 2018; World Health Organization, 2018). Especially significant is the recent alignment of the American Psychological Association (APA) with those recommendations. The APA emphasizes that the "*respect for human rights is central to psychological ethics*", while promoting the adoption of a human rights framework to mental health which develops innovative anti-racist methods, permits equal access and participation towards mental health, and advocates for human rights, especially including those from marginalized populations or settings (APA, 2021).

These proposals must mark the path that will overcome the perspective that medicalizes the psychological suffering caused by the experiences of disadvantage and discrimination in the Romani populations across Europe. Not only does it seek to empower the Romani population maintaining unfair living conditions and asymmetric power relations in institutions and social fabric. Attention must also be paid to the need to put the power—influence—in the hands of local actors. It is a matter of generating conditions that give real power to communities in extremely disadvantaged conditions, including those whose psychological suffering as a priority (Miranda et al., 2020; Trickett, 2009).

How Can We Use the Existing Knowledge of Romani Mental Health to Strengthen a Human Rights-Based Approach?

In this section we will map existing knowledge about Romani people and the lessons learned from other racialized groups in the world to provide guidance in the field of Romani mental health in Europe. As it is depicted in the Figure 2, we adopted a collaborative methodology to map the state of the art of RMH from a human rights-based analytical framework, that included the meaningful participation of key stakeholders. The participants included a consortium of organizations from Italy, Ukraine, Germany and Czech Republic—with varied backgrounds and professions, for example: researchers, medical professionals, grassroots leaders and health care professionals.

Figure 2. Methodological approach in the development of this report

The objective was to involve all actors to increase the capacity of researchers to co-create knowledge, practice reflexivity, and adopt approaches that empower communities to define themselves, and their needs (Miranda et al., 2020). As reflected in Annex 1, we held two one-on-one meetings with each consortium to discuss the proposed framework and their initial findings. Next, we reviewed the findings and incorporated them into the analytical framework. To support their findings and the framework we mapped available scientific evidence. A survey was developed based on these findings and our first meetings (See Annex 2). The objective of this survey was to prioritize discussion and build the workshop agenda. A three-part workshop brought together all participants and the external experts to discuss Romani mental health from a human rights-based framework. The objective was to build on the findings and define a series of recommendations and next steps. Researchers took field notes of the meetings and workshops. Finally, the field notes from the workshop and survey responses were categorized into overarching themes. The document was uploaded to a shared platform to receive feedback from the participants over the course of two weeks. These comments were included to update the draft.

The findings presented below can help understand certain characteristics of mental distress and mental wellbeing in Romani communities, as well as serving as a base to highlight the need of adopting non-medical perspectives for further research. In each section we present key findings from the consortium and a summary of the literature found to support and build on the human rights-

based analytical framework to RMH. We emphasize the direct impact that each determinant has in shaping the experiences of mental distress and mental wellbeing while underlining the interdependent and interrelated nature of all of them in conforming a unique and complex psychological experience in the Romani population. Although extensive evidence were found on mental health status and determinants among different racialized groups, only a summary of the literature found is presented, though the entire list of references included in this review can be found on Annex 3.

Romani Mental Distress Understood as Experiences of Social Disadvantage

As it is depicted in Table 1, findings from the three participating consortia and the data available in the scientific literature coincide on the fact that Romani and other minoritized groups usually report higher mental distress than the majority population throughout all age samples, including the elderly, adults and children and adolescents.

Table 1. *Romani Mental Distress: Key findings from the Germany & Czech Republic, Italy and Ukraine consortia*

Germany & Czech Republic	Findings from interviews with Romani communities in Germany and Czech Republic regarding the identity of distress show that the most common problems they named were “Anger/Anxiety/Fear”, “Depression/Sadness”, “Stress”, “Mental problems/Nerves” and traumatic events.
	Furthermore, some interviewees named the cause of their distress, specifying “Problems with identity as Sinti/Roma” and “Discrimination”, as well as “Fear/Stress/Pressure”, “stressful/ traumatic events” and “financial problems”. Moreover, alcohol and drug use were mentioned as ways of getting over distress.
Italy	Most common mental health issues in Romani populations living in formal or informal camps in Italy -in which Romani communities face high levels of poverty and multiple social disadvantages- are anxiety, depression, drug and alcohol use. Complex bereavement is also relevant within these communities. Furthermore, women and children are at greater risk of suffering mental distress.
Ukraine	Results from the survey in Romani communities in Ukraine show that 41.06% of the Romani sample had signs of mild depression, 20.85% had signs of moderate depression, and 11.97% had signs of severe depression. Similarly, 39.64% of Romani respondents have signs of mild anxiety, 22.78% medium and 6.82% high.

Different sources also coincide on recognizing that Romani adults suffer higher levels of mental difficulties than non-Romani population, including a higher prevalence of depression, anxiety or psychotic symptoms. Other mental distress indicators such as dissatisfaction with life, unhappiness or lower wellbeing, quality of life or self-perceived health status are salient in the literature (Lê Cook,

Progovac and Tran, 2019; Cvjetkovic, Jankovic and Bjegovic-Mikanovic, 2017; Kamberi, Martinovic and Verkuyten, 2015; Cook et al., 2013; Janevic, Jankovic, & Bradley, 2012; Hassler and Eklund, 2012). On the other hand, the prevalence of tobacco smoking, binge drinking or illicit substance use among Romani population is also reported to be various points higher than the rest of the population. This is usually as a consequence of experiencing multiple traumatic events, turning substance use into the strategy to cope with discrimination experiences (Chomynová et al., 2020).

Special focus must be placed on most at-risk groups, such as Roma Travellers, women or children and adolescents. A large part of the publications on the literature review refer to Roma Travellers, nomadic communities established mainly in the United Kingdom and Ireland, whose living conditions and lifestyles may differ considerably from the circumstances in which Romani people live in other European contexts. Thus, most of the publications agree that the main mental health problems they report are depression and anxiety (Lane and Tribe, 2010) and a higher incidence of suicides in these communities (Yin Har and Ridge, 2011).

Just as the consortia, literature highlights women are at higher risk of experiencing mental distress, since they may experience a doubled discrimination, due to the mere fact of being women and being Romani. Different studies report that Romani women show higher number of symptoms of depression, anxiety, phobias, sleep problems, disinterest or somatizations, migraines or alcohol consumption, as well as poorer perceived health (Cook et al., 2013; Janevic et al., 2012; Carrasco-Garrido et al., 2011).

Children and adolescents are also emphasized as one of the groups at higher risk of experiencing mental distress by the three consortia, which is further supported by literature review findings. Romani teenagers usually report suffering a higher number of mental distress indicators, such as lower wellbeing, positive affect, life satisfaction and higher rates of hopelessness (Dimitrova et al., 2017; Cook et al., 2013; Dimitrova, 2013).

Experiences of social disadvantage among other ethnic groups throughout the world are also related to higher prevalence of mental distress or other psychiatric symptoms. In the United States, depression is reported as the most relevant and prevalent symptom in racialized groups, such as Asian Americans, Hispanics and Blacks, among others (Kalibatseva et al., 2017; Jang, Park, Kang & Chiriboga, 2013; Walsemann, Bell and Goosby., 2011; Walsemann, Bell and Maitra, 2011; Herrera et al., 2010). Stress and trauma were also reported as prevalent symptoms on USA's ethnic mistreated groups (Jabson et al., 2016), significantly associated with poorer mental wellbeing and life satisfaction or higher substance use (Kim & Fredriksen-Goldsen, 2016; Na & Hample, 2016; McNeil et al., 2015).

In addition, evidence on mental health among the most vulnerable groups of Romani communities are concordant with findings on other racialized groups worldwide. Data on higher depressive symptoms on Romani women coincide with the situation of female and Black participants in the United States (Jackson & Goodman, 2011). Similarly, the situation of children and adolescents from other racialized groups coincide with that of the Romani youth- i.e. mental health differences have been found between those with indigenous and not indigenous mothers, differences that stayed significant even when controlling for family and neighborhood characteristics (Priest, Baxter & Hayes, 2012). Racial/ethnic disparities across all measures of health-related quality of life and health status, favoring White children and especially disfavoring Hispanic and African American children (Wallander et al., 2012), even after adjusting for socioeconomic status and family contextual differences.

As anticipated, these evidences show that the mental distress suffered by the Romani population—as well as other ethnic racialized groups—is associated with the impact that structural discrimination and social exclusion have on their psychological outcomes and the cost of the coping processes they

deploy. Discrimination, exclusion and internalization interact in a positive feedback loop that traps them and extremely impairs their lives. To gain an in-depth understanding of the determinants of mental health in Romani populations, it is necessary to know how each component individually influences their mental health and how they interact with each one another. Next, we will describe each of these processes (i.e., structural discrimination, exclusion from social spheres and internalization of trauma).

Structural Discrimination as a Determinant of Mental Distress

Findings from the three participating consortia, affirm that several structural and systemic conditions that usually surround Romani and other ethnic mistreated groups are decisive for the deterioration of their mental health status – i.e. neighborhood characteristics, barriers to access to education and to scale in the education system, unfair and substandard living and housing conditions or poverty. Table 2 reflects on the findings from the Germany & Czech Republic, Italy and Ukraine consortia.

Table 2. *Key findings from the Italy and Ukraine consortia on Structural Discrimination*

Germany & Czech Republic	Quantitative results show that causes of distress are mostly psychosocial, especially stress and worry, but also racism, “his/her culture/way of life, and bereavement or loss.
Italy	<p>Roma and Sinti communities in Italy are exposed to discrimination, constant hate speech, emergency social practices, ghettoizing housing policies and constant infringement of their human rights, generating dysfunctional behaviors, reducing their resources for managing situations and difficulties projecting themselves into the future. Also, these circumstances often lead to inability to manage everyday life emotionally, use of drugs and alcohol, aggressive behaviour or passivity towards society</p> <p>Social determinants also influence the political attitude towards Roma and Sinti, based on externally imposed identity and linked with racist perceptions. Italian Roma undergo a socially accepted racism, which is reflected in legal provisions application also.</p> <hr/> <p>Mental distress in Romani populations are closely related to social health determinants, such as housing conditions, education, employment, SES (socioeconomic status) and lifestyles. The constant influence of discrimination, prejudice and racism over Romani’s lives worsens mental health outcomes and marginalization, as well as a splitting process and a detachment from a devalued external world, a tolerance attitude and powerlessness</p>
Ukraine	<p>Results from the survey completed by Romani communities in Ukraine support that life satisfaction grows in direct proportion to the level of education; also, those who have a permanent job or work for themselves have the highest satisfaction rates in various spheres of life.</p> <p>Regarding access to services, indicators of geographical accessibility and Roma friendliness, are quite low, which significantly determine the ability to use the services, and the ability to meet the needs related to the psychological wellbeing of Romani adults and children.</p>

Consortia findings are consistent with those observed in other studies of Romani and other oppressed racialized groups, as well as the domains identified in the European framework as structural determinants of Roma inequities; i.e., housing, employment and education.

Overwhelming evidences show that living in neighborhoods that are isolated can deteriorate the individual level of wellbeing due to the relational aspects between neighbors as well as the lack of access to resources and services. For instance, Vazsonyi et al. (2020) observed that fear or concerns about neighborhood safety, neighborhood acquaintanceship density and nighttime social activities were important in internalizing and externalizing mental health disorders in a sample of Romani adolescents. But this is not only an exclusive result among Romani people; similarly, Franco, Pottick & Huang, 2010 found that there is a greater level of parental distress in neighborhoods with high social disorder and low social cohesion among white, blacks and Hispanics living in disenfranchised conditions. Conversely, it is clearly documented that when Romani populations enjoy dignified living conditions, they report good scores of psychological well-being.

Another direct impact of structural discrimination on the mental health of the Romani population is linked to difficulties in obtaining fair employment conditions and financial security. The chain reaction of unemployment on financial stress, such as indebtedness and the need to rely on abusive loansharks causes mental distress for individuals and families (Sterthal, Slopen & Williams, 2011). Chomynová and colleagues (2020) have documented that unemployment was the most severe problem perceived among Romani communities from the Czech Republic due to its association with low quality of housing, loansharking, bad hygienic conditions or sexual abuses. Specifically, sexual discrimination has been found to increase suicidal ideation/attempts by racial and ethnic groups who suffer similar structural discrimination as Romani communities (Feinstein et al., 2019).

Marginalization among Romani populations is also reflected in the barriers to access to education with equal opportunities and equal conditions to the rest of the population. Financial constraints limit access to education with guarantees and pushes them into segregated education. This has a direct negative impact on the well-being of members of racialized ethnic groups as it has been documented, for instance, by Walsemann, Bell and Glosby (2011) in a sample of African American and black Caribbean communities. These inequities also have a moderator role in the deterioration of the psychological wellbeing through limiting academic performance and avoiding the scaling of the educational levels. In fact, Marshall-Fabien & Miller (2016) found that low educational level is significantly associated with depressive symptoms among ethnic mistreated groups who suffer structural discrimination.

These circumstances of structural discrimination also have a direct impact on the mental health of the European Romani population who find themselves losing their sense of identity due to the threats and pressures of conforming to living like the mainstream society. Heaslip, Hean and Parker (2016) found six characteristics of psychological vulnerability among Romani Travellers, including 1) feeling homogenized as a group; 2) being pressured to conform to living a certain way; 3) a split in their identities; 4) loss of cultural heritage; 5) feeling discriminated against, persecuted and threatened and 6) feeling that they have no voice. The worst part is suffered, once again, by women. The intersection of gender adds layers of stigma and affects health outcomes both within and outside the community. Yin Har and Ridge (2011) observed that gender discrimination and violence within Romani communities affect the women's mental health seriously.

Key points

- These are clear expressions of their feelings of helplessness, powerlessness and hopelessness due to structural discrimination.

- Multiple minority identities that are intertwined in structural discrimination (i.e. ethnic, gender, sexual or social class identities) put people at risk for severe mental distress, in some cases suicide.
- The constant influence of discrimination, prejudice and racism over Romani's lives worsens conditions of isolation and marginalization (reflected through poorer opportunities to attain fair living conditions), affecting mental health outcomes.
- Accessibility and responsiveness of services significantly determine the ability to use the services, and the ability to meet the needs related to the psychological wellbeing of Romani people.

Exclusion from Social Spheres as a Determinant of Mental Distress

Living in isolation creates barriers to accessing resources, causing the exclusion from social spheres and impeding Romani communities from building diverse and supportive social networks that are needed for healthy conditions. Literature review findings coincide with Italian and Ukrainian research findings.

Table 3. *Key findings from the Italy and Ukraine consortia on exclusion from the social spheres.*

Italy	Living in segregated settlements can expose minors to isolation (hardships in the social inclusion process and lack of personal safety, due to exposition to racist episodes); negative experiences (inadequate ways of managing emotions, increased fear, rage, sadness, and in some cases violence) and passivity (due to the extreme precariousness resources).
Ukraine	Results obtained through focus groups show that employment, financial status, education and discrimination are the main social determinants that affect Romani mental wellbeing, specifically, discrimination against Roma. Cultural determinants of Romani mental wellbeing are mainly the community, family, age, and gender; outside their community, Romani feel more vulnerable.

Social networks are where individuals find resources for social support, a sense of belonging and commitment, reciprocity and social references. Social networks are comprised of our most intimate relationships like family, friends, children, and partners as well as those we spend time with in other social settings –such as the community found in faith-based settings, schools, civil society organizations, or jobs, among others. As reflected from the Italian consortium findings, many Romani communities in Europe live isolated whether because of a settlement or in marginalized neighborhoods in larger cities. This isolation limits social networks and creates denser relationships with the immediate community, without ties to the outside world. Dense relationships with the immediate community mean that it plays a determining factor in individual wellbeing. According to Nystad, Spein & Ingstad (2014), same networks cause stress for Sami adolescents if they feel they are excluded and demanded to conform to the ethnic group. The expectation to care and show responsibility to others through these networks can also be associated with pressure especially when

the group value assumes more importance than the individual. Foster and colleagues (2019) found that Hispanic, Black and Asian communities influence of family conflict, including adverse childhood experiences, is associated with increasing mental distress symptoms and lower wellbeing.

Isolated conditions cause a lack of social connectedness which is reported as a key determinant of several racialized groups' mental health. The ability to influence others and be recognized by others are important aspects beneficial for mental health status. When a person feels marginalized, lacking influence over others, one's community becomes an unpredictable, insecure place, serving to increase vulnerability to stressors. For instance, Walton (2018) showed that narratives reveal how Whites have more access to the mental health benefits of sense of community (through the perception of greater and more effective mutual influence) than Blacks.

Intrapersonal interactions shape an individual experience. Multiple publications demonstrate that factors such as major and everyday discrimination or bad treatment perpetrated by majority populations towards racialized groups are associated with poorer mental health outcomes, such as depression, lower satisfaction with life, lower self-esteem, suicide symptoms or school belonging. Benner and Wang (2017) found that Latino and Asians who experience peer-perpetrated discrimination and teacher-perpetrated discrimination were the factors that predicted lower levels of mental wellbeing. The effects of structural discrimination causes a gap between minorities and majority population.

Key points

- Exclusion from social spheres cause distrust between majority and minoritized communities, feelings of isolation and conflict.
- Romani mental health is affected by isolation and a one-faceted social network that is caused by discrimination,
- Dense social networks can increase the importance of group value over that individual value, which in turn individuals can feel pressured to conform to the group norms.
- Feeling influential and important to others plays a special role on social network dynamics, with positive consequences on mental wellbeing.

Transmitted Trauma and Interiorized Discrimination as Determinants of Mental Distress

The relationship between structural discrimination and the exclusion from social spheres suffered by Romani people cause trauma as well as the interiorization of the discriminative experiences at the individual level. Isolation and social comparisons enhance interiorized oppression experiences and Romani mental distress, by believing negative stigma about themselves, giving rise to feelings of worthlessness and powerlessness as well as lower self-esteem. This situation can be easily reflected through German and Czech Republic consortia findings, which report how transgenerational trauma due to Nazi genocide still shapes RMH, including distrust towards other people as well as poor self-empowerment and identity hiding.

Table 4. *Key findings from the Germany & Czech Republic consortium on transmitted trauma and interiorized discrimination.*

Germany & Czech Republic	<p>Lack of trust due to history and the continuing discrimination by the majority society is a prominent topic, especially toward s German Sinti/Roma communities due to the impact that Nazi genocide still has on their living situations, and thus, on mental health.</p> <hr/> <p>In many cases, a transgenerational transmission of trauma can be observed in the Sinti/Roma communities: traumatizing experiences of Sinti/Roma survivors of the Nazi genocide are present in the second/third/fourth generation and shape daily life and attitudes towards mental health.</p> <hr/> <p>Continuous traumatic experiences often lead to hiding one's own identity, in order not to be exposed to further trauma, which has a strong influence on psychological wellbeing and possibilities of self-empowerment.</p>
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According to consortia findings, the historical discrimination transmitted from generation to generation are embedded in the Romani ethnic identity. Consequently, identifying oneself with an ethnic or racial group can yield negative emotions that harm individual self-concept, but also can increase perceived discrimination. Dimitrova et al. (2017) found that, in different European countries, Romani ethnic identity correlates negatively with personal wellbeing. Moreover, Begeny and Huo (2017) found that feeling valued among ingroup members turned ethnic identity more central to self-concept in Asian and Latinos, associated with lower mental health and more perceptions of discrimination.

Through social interactions, perceived discrimination is also attributed to race and ethnicity, perception that worsens mental wellbeing. Hu & Taylor (2016) found that awareness of ethnicity during social interactions among Asian Americans and Latinos was associated with more depressive symptoms, stress, irritability, suspicion and resentment. Race/ethnicity was also found to be the most frequent attribution for perceived discrimination among African Americans and Caribbean Black youth, having those who attribute discrimination to physical appearance worse psychological wellbeing (Seaton et al., 2010).

Finally, perceived discrimination and internalized racism have effects on individual self-esteem and sense of control. In a sample of South Africans, discrimination and life events were inversely related to mastery and self-esteem even after controlling stress (Williams et al., 2012). Internalized racism diminishes racial identification among African Americans, resulting in lower levels of mastery and higher depressive symptoms (Hughes, Kiecolt, Keith & Demo, 2015).

Key points

- The Romani identity is linked to higher probabilities of mental distress outside of Romani communities.
- The awareness of ethnicity during social interactions was associated with more depressive symptoms, stress, irritability, suspicion and resentment, through the effects of perceived discrimination.

- Everyday discrimination, understood as the precursor of internalized racism, is associated with poorer mental health outcomes, such as depression, lower life satisfaction, lower self-esteem or suicide symptoms.

Romani Mental Wellbeing Understood as Feeling Recognized and Influential

Protecting human rights promotes feelings of recognition and influence within Romani populations, enhancing mental wellbeing. Nevertheless, this can only be achieved through a process where Romani people firstly build on critical awareness and strengths, then building social networks and capacity to respond and lastly, through the development of transformative multilevel changes.

Although previous pieces of evidence seem to affirm that racialized groups generally suffer greater mental health challenges, other studies have highlighted the strengths of Romani populations and other minorities to preserve their wellbeing, i.e. some researchers have found that Romani population report more happiness and life satisfaction, as well as similar levels of well-being to those of the majority population, in different European countries (Lim, Cappa and Patton, 2017; Cook et al., 2013).

Critical Awareness and Strengths as a Component of Romani Mental Wellbeing

To ensure Romani mental wellbeing, liberation tools as critical awareness and highlighting strengths must be built, in order to promote capacity to respond and take action against oppressive conditions (Garcia-Ramirez et al, 2011). In fact, German and Czech Republic partners recognize the relevance of psychoeducational processes to raise awareness on mental distress.

Table 6. *Key findings from the Germany & Czech Republic consortium on “Critical Awareness and Strengths” specifically.*

Germany & Czech Republic	Coping behaviors in Sinti/Roma Czech and German communities includes mostly social activities like talking to someone and spending time with others, but also private activities like thinking, being busy with something and praying.
	The answers indicate that some mental challenges cannot be recognized as such in the absence of psychoeducational knowledge. A focus of the interviews and group discussions was an elaboration of empowerment factors, that play a crucial role in psychoeducation and health literacy: awareness of traumatization; psychosocial approaches (within the community); person-centered approaches (e.g. peer counselling as an approach in contrast to non-medical help).
	Professional help was found to be considered important among Romani respondents, although they had little experience with it, which indicates the

potential of self-empowerment. Nevertheless, lack of access, discrimination, ignorance or inhibitions have led to not accepting professional help.

Throughout the literature review only a couple of studies were found to support findings from the Germany & Czech Republic consortia regarding critical awareness and strengths, probably as a consequence of using keywords usually related to clinical settings on the literature review, hiding findings focused on community empowerment matters.

Peer-run programs and community-based programs were found to benefit their community. These types of programs increased empathy due to shared experiences, freedom to talk and humanization. Participants from a study done on LGBTQ of color in the US expressed previous lack of information in their communities, which increased stereotypes, blame, shame and silence; highlighting how identity intersections affect discrimination and the lack of community support. Participants expressed that ethnic community-specific programs are needed; sharing cultures and experiences would be beneficial (Holley et al., 2019).

Also, innovative ongoing community-based initiatives can be relevant to enhance critical awareness among marginalized groups. Pavlovski & Frishchikj (2017) are developing new research projects focusing on building capacity and awareness among Romani communities in Macedonia, within a framework based on social accountability and legal empowerment aimed at health advocacy. Other research has been focused on raising awareness on reproductive and sexual rights –as well as existing resources on their communities to overcome unequal conditions– among Roma women and girls in diverse European countries, following a reproductive justice approach (Garcia-Ramirez et al., 2020).

Key points

- Spaces that promote empathy between people of the same identify group to share their experiences promotes wellbeing.
- Psychoeducational knowledge, health literacy, legal empowerment or reproductive justice principles are important aspects to consider in program planning.
- Identify empowerment within programs is needed to combat feelings of shame, blame and silence.

Building Networks and Capacity to Respond as a Determinant of Mental Wellbeing

Critical awareness and strengths must be complemented with capacity to create new social. To build networks, it is essential to identify support and allies in the community, i.e. organizations, local public officials, informal groups, community leaders, religious groups.

Social support is usually found as one of the main predictors of mental wellbeing, including evidences from the three consortia. However, social networks and support reported usually entail family and community networks only.

Table 7. Key findings from the Germany & Czech Republic, Italy and Ukraine consortia on “Building Networks and Capacity to Respond” specifically.

Germany & Czech Republic	In German and Czech Republic, Roma/ Sinti communities find relevant support in their families, being the problems discussed usually with family members, though at the same time these conversations were viewed negatively.
	Regarding psychosocial offers and adaptations within these communities, family was also found to be a buffer that opens many resources.
Italy	Within the experience of discrimination, Italian partners found that in Romani communities, the family is at the same time an escape goat (against which to unload frustration), a protective niche (to protect oneself and find validation) and a bond (something that limits your possibilities and gives you no alternatives).
Ukraine	The cohesion of the Romani community, the supportive role of family and especially the Romani women, as well as the authority of older people are found to be the cultural factors that support mental health in Ukrainian Romani communities. Nevertheless, family situations can be both empowerment and powerless, although the community is primarily a supportive and inspiring factor for Romani.

Multiple evidence demonstrates the positive role that strong family attachments have on wellbeing. Relational commitment enhances capacity to resist mental distress, such as the family and religious identity are positively related to the well-being of Romani people (Dimitrova et al., 2017). Also, among Roma Travellers, the strong family attachments are important in supporting them through physical and practical struggles (Rogers, 2015).

Perceived social support and social connectedness was found to prevent mental distress. In fact, strong social support and high social integration are negatively associated with depression among Blacks and Latinos (Yang & Park, 2019), while cross-cultural socialization as well as emotional support was positively associated with multiple facets of psychosocial well-being (positive relations with self-perceptions and interpersonal relationship quality; negative link with externalizing behaviors) (Wang et al., 2020).

Social participation plays an important role in maintaining wellbeing. Overall community engagement or participation in faith-based organizations are relevant for disease prevention and management. Herrera et al. (2010) found that greater participation in social activities was significantly associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms. Indeed, on stress management, native American youth highlighted issues such as connecting with valued others or engaging in meaningful activities (Kelley & Lowe, 2012), while African American women with persistent Community Engagement were significantly more likely to report better self-rated health, less frequent anxious mood, and less frequent depressed mood (Fothergill et al., 2011). On the other hand, being part of social or religious communities, for example, the Evangelical Church, is known to promote well-being among Romani, since it reinforces self-esteem, empowerment and the feeling of belonging (Amador, Flecha and Sordé, 2018).

Key points

- Social support/networks are relevant to prevent mental distress for people experiencing discrimination whether this support is from family, peers, religious groups or spirituality.
- Romani youth experiencing relational commitment in acts as a key factor for wellbeing. Feeling connected to your ethnic group is positively associated with well-being.
- Participation in social events and community engagement, including ingroup and outgroup activities, is related to better mental health outcomes.

Transformative Multi-Level Change as Determinant of Mental Wellbeing

Since anti-Romani sentiment is present across all these levels; actions led by the community must be done across each of them, for which building critical awareness and strengths, as well as networks and capacity to respond are needed. Transformative multi-level change then must include access to better opportunities as well as meaningful Romani participation and representation, as reflected in consortia findings.

Table 8. Key findings from the Ukraine and Germany & Czech Republic consortia on “Transformative Multi-Level Change” specifically

Ukraine	Because of persistent stereotypes about members of the Romani community by the major society, Romani are likely to face discrimination in various areas. Despite this, Romani respondents in Ukraine see an opportunity to gradually change these stereotypes through their own positive examples.
Germany & Czech Republic	Findings indicate Romani people feel that they are able to do something for themselves and take action of the injustices that they still suffer.

Participation in economic and social spheres through access to better opportunities can bring about psychological wellbeing both for parents and children. It has been verified that certain factors correlate positively with Romani wellbeing and satisfaction with life, such as belonging to the middle or upper class (Cvetkovic et al., 2017) or having access to higher educational level (Gómez-Berrocal, Porrás and Mata, 2020). Pappa et al., (2015) report in a sample of Romani that access to basic material resources (electricity, indoor drainage, and drinkable water) are associated with higher scores on most scales of health-related quality of life. Accordingly, Kim et al. (2017) reported that parental social status (indicated by family income and educational attainment) was significantly related to psychosocial health related quality of life in Blacks, Latinos, and Whites.

Influencing change across community and political settings found that advocacy work can increase Romani community self-perception and wellbeing. Through advocacy, communities learn skills—public speaking and identify daily forms of discrimination—where they feel seen and heard (Miranda et al, 2020). Finally, meaningful representation and feeling reflected with role models for racialized children and adolescents is related to wellbeing. For example, watching the film *Black Panther* (which principal actor -and hero- was Black) in school in the United States increased empowerment significantly between Black/African Americans, while also having a significant effect on wellbeing

among Black/African Americans and Asian Americans (Allende González-Velázquez, Shackelford, Keller, Vinney & Drake, 2020).

Key points

- Identifying positive examples, or representation can help combat discrimination and enhance psychological wellbeing.
- Better positions economically and socially protect ethnic youth from mental distress and internalizing stigma.

Where Do We Go from Here?

In this section we provide a series of key points to further our discussion based on (1) consortia findings; (2) priorities from survey, (3) answers to open-ended survey questions; (4) guidelines provided from external experts and (5) the conversations held during a series of workshops between November and December 2020. The information has been grouped into a series overarching questions. Next, we address each question with a practical example for each.

How We Can We Develop Free-Violence Research Approaches

Research approaches “others” Romani communities. This is a violent action and creates a superiority complex between researchers and community, in a form that can be interpreted as dehumanization. Anti-racism in the field of wellbeing research considers cultural aspects of the communities with whom we work and includes mechanisms to repair the damage caused by racial discrimination, aggression or racism. This is done through the recognition of power imbalances, racism, the real needs of minorities and a humanistic approach (Cénat, 2020). In this way, we can do meaningful research based on the real concerns of the community and ensuring they are protagonists (Suarez-Balcazar, 2020). The following are aspects we have identified:

- Explicitly addressing cultural domination, Whiteness and researcher entitlement within academia and evaluation processes, for examples, measures should be developed by Romani, their knowledge valued and included in the research process. Non-Romani researchers need to recognize the asymmetrical power within the research process and show political solidarity by taking a step back and allowing Romani to be the protagonists. These are ways to build trust and take away “researcher entitlement”
- Research settings should be “safe spaces” that are free of violence, that means practicing cultural humility and addressing daily experiences of violence.
- Legitimizing Romani knowledge as scientific evidence to challenge dominant, non-Romani science. For example, turning communities’ experiences into data that can be utilized for advocacy purposes.
- Treating Romani as (co-)researchers in the design and implementation of studies and not only research participants, this includes recognizing their time and work through equal pay.
- Ensuring that research about Romani is being transferred back to the community, devolving the knowledge and not simply for researcher gains.
- Changing the parameters of “expert” knowledge

Example. Building the collaborative capacity for meaningful community participation.

In 2016 the International Organization for Migrations took part in the evaluation of the National Roma Integration Strategies health component (NRIS-H) across member states through the Equi-Health project. In Spain, the evaluation model developed at the national level included both evidence-based and narrative-based knowledge from a range from stakeholders to review the impact of NRIS-H. The aim was to promote shared understanding between multiple people in order to better plan for the future of Roma health policies. Lessons learned from this initiative highlighted the lack of meaningful Roma participation through the NRIS design, implementation and evaluation stages (Escobar-Ballesta et al, 2018).

These conclusions were then translated to the local level context to ensure Roma health governance in the Poligono Sur (Seville), a marginalized neighborhood with a high Roma population. This process built the capacity of local Roma leaders to take part in defining health priorities, considering the community as experts in the research process. Non-Roma, university-based researchers acted as facilitators of the process to ensure Roma leadership in local policy-making and expertise in gathering and reviewing the evidence. At the same time anti-Roma discrimination was addressed with non-Roma health care providers from the national healthcare system. Roma community knowledge was used as the basis for advocacy efforts (Miranda et al., 2019).

In specific, a group of Roma women identified issues that mattered to them and collected evidence through photographs, narratives and survey interviews to other self-identified Roma neighbors. Through a series of meetings, researchers and neighbors analyzed and developed conclusions about Roma health inequities at the local level. These conclusions were developed into PowerPoint presentations and reports to gain support and advocate for just conditions. With the support of researchers, the group of women organized into a grassroots initiative called YILÓ (meaning heart in Romani language). Their goal is to ensure that community knowledge is at the forefront. The process was replicated during the COVID-19 crisis.

For more information please see: <https://cespyd.es/en/news/advocating-for-roma-rights-in-the-face-of-the-coronavirus-crisis/>

How We Can Adopt a Community Development and Organizing Approach

Community development is understood as shifting power back to residents at the local level to determine local agendas and allocation of resources (Christens, 2012; Kegler et al, 2019). This entails a developing critical consciousness of discriminatory situations, developing new networks, alliances and supports through organizing efforts and acting to change unjust living conditions (Balcazar et al, 2011). This type of approach entails:

- Developing critical knowledge with the community in which Romani people can gain understanding of daily discrimination and express with peers, as a form of peer support.
- Including aspects of legal empowerment in which Romani people gain awareness of their rights.

- Health empowerment through informative meetings on mental health, and orientation on why and how users can access public mental health local services
- Creating alliances between non-Romani and Romani civil society based on transparency and reflexivity.
- Strengthening Romani organizations as agents of change within the community.
- Supporting Romani self-organization and pro-Romani structures at the local level. Not only consolidated organizations but informal groups of activists that are many times made invisible by the powerful organizations.
- Implementing local level advocacy that is led by the community that in turn develops their skills to articulate what is happening in their community while defending their rights.
- Identifying informal opportunities to promote participation at the local level--local meetings, art festivals, cultural events, coffee shops.
- Including the voices of Romani experiencing the most vulnerability and be mindful of creating a gap between Romani leaders and those living in marginalized contexts. We must develop the capacity of Romani communities and distribute the power and gateway into the community.
- Taking an intersectional approach to community development, focusing on Romani women and youth in decision-making spaces.
- Working on the local level will help to overcome homogenizing the Romani experience which will promote responses adequate to specific needs.

Example. Pilot Workshop of a Human Rights-based Approach to Roma Mental Health in Macedonia.

Based on the findings from this report, CESPYD collaborated with Macedonian colleagues from five Roma non-governmental organizations (NGO) to implement a Human Rights-based approach in their advocacy work. Organizational managers and community animators who were working at the community level participated in this three-part capacity-building workshop.

Module 1. CESPYD shared the theoretical framework and a series of good practices in order to build a common language using visual aids such as posters, videos, presentations. The module ended with a discussion that linked participants' personal and group experiences to the shared framework of Roma mental health from a human rights-based approach. Through dialogue we linked the social determinants of health to a biopsychosocial model, connecting this to the realities in their different local contexts. By identifying different issues, CEPSPYD facilitated the dialogue to explore the causes and consequences on Roma mental health.

Module 2. In order to gain capacity to articulate ideas and prioritize local, relevant issues regarding Roma mental health and wellbeing a nominal group methodology was utilized. The three most voted issues were used to build an advocacy plan in Module 3.

Module 3. In this final module participants identified and discussed the following items: target (policy, institutional/organizational, community), objective, action, allies, barriers and timeline. At the end of the session participants will group back together to share the results of their advocacy plans and commit to their implementation. An additional follow-up session will be carried out to check the implementation of the plan and for technical assistance.

The five NGO advocacy plans consisted of the following objectives:

- To raise awareness about the importance of preschool education
- To reduce barriers between social services and Roma communities
- To increase to healthcare service during COVID-19 times
- To promote Roma tailored family and planning and education
- To increase social service responsiveness

CESPYD supported NGOs in identifying possible evidence to support the objectives and provided feedback to improve the advocacy plans. This will entail a follow-up session in the upcoming months, as the feedback is an iterative process to ensure improvement.

How we can address discrimination at multiple levels

We understand that discrimination is present and transmitted across individual, interpersonal, organizational, community and political levels, therefore, needs to be addressed by working across all to dismantle institutionalized of racism (Griffith et al., 2007). In concrete:

- Raising awareness in various settings while gaining alliances to advocate for Romani communities--schools, healthcare centers, universities, community-level, policy level and identify alliances in each of these to be advocates within their organizations. For example, working with health care professionals or teachers.

- Ensuring accountability of discrimination at every level--media, police, schools, public administrations. This includes reparations and justice for historical discrimination.
- Creating a space for cooperation between Romani and non-Romani experts, organizations and public services professionals to build a functional system-- for example building local coalitions that bridges multiple levels as ensures that Romani mental health is included in different agendas.
- Non-Romani people should work at dismantling their interiorized violence against Romani people.
- Addressing daily forms of discriminations--or microaggression in everyday exchanges.
- Identifying issues - for example, the Romani settlements in Italy - that mirror aspects of institutionalization and are now widely accepted forms of discrimination that affect mental health.

Example. *European Public Health Alliance Roma Health Network.*

The Roma Health Network (RHN) is an EU level advocacy platform established by the European Public Health Alliance that brings together Roma experts, advocates, researchers and governmental workers across different member states. This platform urges collaboration between its members for research, position statements and meetings to review emerging issues and opportunities for policy advocacy. RHN sheds light on the local and national level issues to the European level. For example, local level issues are included in the monthly newsletter, guest articles on their website that is disseminated across Europe. EPHA colleagues identify opportunities for advocacy to bring up local issues and ensure local Roma voices are heard across levels.

At the launch of the Roma Health Network, researchers from CESPYPD were able to promote the voices of Roma women from the grassroots organization, YILÓ, in front of European level stakeholders and national stakeholders from different countries. The women were asked about addressing barriers to participation, and grouped their ideas into four strategies they proposed to improve it:

- Having resources and opportunities: *“We have no peace of mind with the daily economic pressures. If we all had a job, this neighborhood would change.”*
- Recognition: *“There is so much opposition to us, that we ourselves believe that we are not worthy. We have to change that. Come live a day in my shoes.”*
- Intersectional approach: *“We have the same problem as all women in this society, but we have our own ways of living that creates other challenges for us.”*
- Promote capacity-building efforts: *“Don’t look at us from up there, empathize with us. Change your position to change your prejudices, don’t teach me HOW to live my life”*

See more at: <https://epha.org/roma-health-network/>

Example. *Roma Civil Society Networks in Spain.*

The Equi-Sastipen-Roma network was created in 2010 with funding of the former Ministry of Health. This network is led and composed by 22 Roma organizations across Spain that develop activities in the field of health. This network is linked to the Health Working Group of the Roma State Council, and actively involves the participation of the Public University of Navarra and the University of Alicante as well as experts from the Ministry of Health.

The Khetané Platform, is a civil society platform, without any link to government institutions, that arose to bring together and represent the entire diversity of the Roma organizational movement in Spain under one common project. The Platform includes the vast majority of organizations represented in the State Council as well as in the Equi-Sastipen-Roma Network.

See more at: <https://plataformakhetane.org/>

How We Can Expand Our Conceptualization of Trauma Towards A Strength-Based Approach

We know that trauma is utilized in a medical framework. We must transform its use and expand its meaning to change that a person becomes a victim because of their adverse experiences. Trauma from a psychosocial perspective is understood as existing on a spectrum and not merely the negative distress responses caused by adversity but also understood from resilience to acquiring new capacities and resources (Papadopoulus, 2007). From this lens it is not someone who is defined by their adverse experience –therefore not linking Romani to the victim identity– but what someone gains from these adverse experiences. Instead:

- Undoing the conflation of trauma with the identity of helpless victim, as could happen in certain clinical environments that closely follow White, dominant approaches that are not sensitive to minorities nor trained in cultural competence.
- Identifying good practices within the medical setting that incorporates a biopsychosocial model.
- Expanding towards a strength-based approach that recognizes the capacity of individuals or groups. This entails focusing on the capacity and the newfound characteristic due to adverse experiences.
- Broaden the horizon of the expert-patient relationship that often can only promote coping mechanism, with transformative approaches that address asymmetrical power structures.
- Supporting people processing and exploring past and daily experiences concerning discrimination
- Increase awareness and instigate motivation to advocate against unfair living conditions.
- Understanding that psychological responses to trauma are not unique to Romani people, but all people experiencing collective violence over generations.
- Taking into consideration the diverse experiences within the Romani groups.

Example. *Family Planning Programs and Reproductive Justice for Romani women and girls*

Family planning practices in Spain overlook the realities of Romani women. Practices from a white, dominant agenda such as the use of contraceptives is encouraged. At a primary healthcare center in Poligono Sur, Spain, the medical staff was interviewed to learn more about a regional Family Planning Program that was implemented in the primary healthcare centers. Good practices were identified that neutralize the low impact of policies by adjusting programs and services to Roma needs. For example, adapting communication efforts to support women with low literacy and taking more time than the protocolized allotted time. Professionals at the healthcare center tailored to be culturally component despite the protocol. Teenage pregnancy dropped significantly in parts of the neighbourhood. Good practices in the medical settings support Roma women in accessing resources that are valuable to them and in turn ensuring reproductive justice. Researchers systemized these good practices to advocate for sensitive healthcare professionals.

Example. *Research Process and Findings from the Germany and Czech Republic Consortium*

The Germany and Czech Republic consortium involved Roma and Sinti experts to ensure that the research process was free of violence and adapted to the characteristics of each context as best as possible. For example, key informant interviews were done with Roma and Sinti experts who had a deeper understanding of how to identify and address issues of trauma. This insight helped to guide the focus group interviews. In their reports they **clearly defined the experts** as the Roma and Sinti communities themselves. The results showed that to address trauma it is important to support Roma and Sinti self-organization efforts. In specific, the conclusions state that to support Roma and Sinti mental health “building trust, enlightenment, self-awareness, and education seem to be basic prerequisites for strengthening the community” in the face of generational trauma and present-day discrimination and violence.

Limitations and Future Work

The most important limitation of our study is the lack of Romani researchers, external experts and grassroots organizers involved in the process. During the development of this document, two Sinti women and over twenty non-Romani participants were present. This disproportionate number of Romani participants is a symptom of the issues that we have identified earlier: who is considered qualified as part of the research process? Are we replicating exclusionary systems and perpetuating discrimination within the research process? Future work must be intentional in ensuring Romani people are included during the discussion, building on and leading efforts reflected in the findings. Whether this is overcoming language barriers with translators or finding innovative ways to bring everyday Romani people together to discuss these issues.

During the research process only a few studies were exclusively done with Romani communities. In concrete, only 22 studies were found. The lack of known studies reiterates that the experience of Romani people's mental wellbeing is a hidden phenomenon. Therefore, we had to rely on the comparisons to other ethnic groups, based in other countries, for example, Latinxs in the United States or indigenous people in Australia. Although we can generalize some basic stressors, identified similar processes for resilience across these ethnic communities, research should continue to shed light on the realities of Romani people. Finally, there was a lack of evidence regarding aspects around promoting mental well-being in Romani and other ethnic communities. The lack of studies to promote Romani and other ethnic mistreated groups wellbeing shows that policies and practices are not being monitored.

Finally, as we have developed this document, we now consider that exploring non-medical approaches to mental health does not mean ignoring the biological aspects that mental distress causes nor the expertise of medical professionals in these endeavors. As proposed by a participating medical professional, we must find synergies between these two approaches to deconstruct dominant narratives within the medical field and collaborate to build approaches that inherently give the community voice, recognition and influence to promote well-being in their communities. Following the tension created with this discussion, we incorporated a pragmatic paradigm to the research process.

Romani mental wellbeing has become an important issue that is hidden from policies and recommendations, research and interventions. In this section we provide a series of next steps at different levels to promote the incorporation of a human rights-based approach to Romani mental wellbeing.

First, we recommend using our findings to contextualize them within the new EU Roma Strategic Framework 2020-2030 (European Commission, 2020). Currently, there are no strategies aimed at Romani mental health in this updated document. Over the last versions of these recommendations, a series of horizontal objectives (i.e. gender, discrimination) have been identified across the main sectoral areas of health, education, employment and housing. We suggest advocating to include Romani mental wellbeing as a horizontal objective across the sectoral areas. Currently, the EU framework promotes "participation, empowerment, cooperation" therefore, it will be important to monitor the changes in mental wellbeing at the local level to build on our findings. Mental wellbeing is an expression of human rights protection, which means that changes in sectoral policies that protect human rights should be closely linked to positive effects in Romani wellbeing.

Next, we should frame Romani mental wellbeing as an urgent need within the COVID-19 crisis. We must consider the effects of severe injustices on Romani people dealing with lockdown regulations in overcrowded housing conditions, poor access to healthcare services, lack of medical supplies to protect from spread, inability to engage in the informal economy and access welfare support and

finally the lack of schooling caused by the digital gap (Korunovska & Jovanovic, 2020). The pandemic has been a glimpse of the devastating effects that these global issues will have on Romani families in the future, which has foreshadowed worsening conditions for them. We have seen across Europe that are directed towards dominant culture, privileged situations—for example, staying confined at home when Romani families had no running water or electricity. These families did not have the privilege to protect themselves from the virus, instead the priorities were basic needs such as food, water, and income. For example, at the national level and local levels, we should create networks to monitor the effects of COVID-19 and develop evidence with community members to shed light on the situation, advocate for change and be a part of the problem-solving dynamic.

Romani women and children should be at the forefront of these objectives, as their inclusion in these changes may have sustainable, long-lasting effects on both the individual and community levels. Due to the aggressive effects the pandemic crisis is having on solidifying traditional gender roles and children's abandonment of schools due to failing responsive measures, program planning should develop supportive networks that help women and children narrate their realities and build skills to defend their needs within political agendas. Many studies were found that supported that being both an ethnic racialized group and sexual minority was a cause for high mental distress. We should consider knowing the experience of Romani sexual minorities who are hidden from the available literature.

We recommend that researcher partners with Romani leaders, grassroots organizations or informal groups to support them in a feedback process similar to the methodology implemented in the development of this document. We must incorporate on-the-ground knowledge as legitimate; we must value it and build on that form a collaborative process. Researchers must question the way they are doing research to ensure that they do not replicate discriminatory structures.

We urge medical professionals to incorporate the biopsychosocial approach in their work as well. This approach will not only address the underlying causes of biological symptoms but will support the medical professional in a more complete approach to find sustainable solutions that address systemic issues. Medical professionals have a unique position to advocate for Romani mental wellbeing and, similar to researchers, should include work with the community

Finally, we understand that we must move towards conditions of justice to promote Romani wellbeing (Stronks et al, 2016). With this overall objective in mind, we hope this paper furthers the discussion about what a human rights-based approach to mental health entails, the multiple roles professionals play in deconstructing dominant approaches and narratives, towards liberating methodologies that promote the mental wellbeing of Romani people.

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Annex 1. Meetings

Step	Date	Attendees	Details
Share findings of consortia and reflect on them in terms of human rights.	04.09.20	Germany/CR	Two meetings were held individually between CESPYPD and consortium. The first meeting, CESPYPD share a human rights-based framework and received consortium feedback. First impressions were shared. A second meeting was held where consortium shared their work and we exchanged conversations about the
	30.09.20	CESPYPD	
	11.09.20 28.09.20	Ukraine CESPYPD	
	30.09.20	Italy	
	21.10.20	CEPSYD	
Strengthening a Human Rights-based Approach to Mental Health	04.11.20	Consortia External experts OSF PHP CESPYPD	Three virtual workshops were conducted in order to build collaborative capacity and identifying strategies to promote Roma mental health. The workshop agenda was based on a survey sent to participants beforehand to take stock of priorities. Two discussants broadly experienced on Romani communities and community-based participatory action research methods participated in the workshop. The last meeting was to reach a consensus between the participants, and
Taking stock of priorities	13.11.20	Consortia External experts OSF PHP CESPYPD	
Reach consensus	02.12.20	Consortia External experts OSF PHP CESPYPD	
Feedback for final report	02.12.20- 12.12.20	Consortia CESPYPD	A first draft of the White Paper was shared on a Google doc with all participants and external experts. They were given two weeks to provide feedback

Annex 2. Prioritization Survey for Workshop Participants

The objective of the survey was to identify priorities to be included in the discussions and ensure that we gave space for individual reflection prior to workshops.

Item	Votes
Generational trauma - social trauma, such as systemic racism, violent conflict and displacement, that can damage communities for generations	11
Psycho-social empowerment - participating actively on their development, building critical awareness, gaining the capacity to respond and taking action for community change	9
Roma children and youth - a special focus on children/youth engagement and education	8
Accessibility of resources - barriers (i.e. language, negative attitudes) or facilitators (Roma mediators) in accessing resources	6
Alliance between non-Roma and Roma civil society - building collaboration and creating alliances between key Roma and non-Roma people	6
Empowering the Roma identity - fighting stigma against the Roma and strengthening Roma communities	5
Roma participation in the evaluation process - Roma at the center of developing the research question, data collection, data analysis and dissemination of results.	5
Antigypsyism - specific racism towards Roma, Sinti, Travellers	4
Addressing discrimination at multiple levels - addressing all levels at which Roma develop, socialize and build their identities	4
Roma women leadership role - incorporate an intersectional approach to RMH	3
Mainstreaming Roma policies - linking Roma strategies to existing policy initiatives	2
Revitalising the role of Roma non-governmental organizations - transition from service-user model towards a capacity-building mode	2
Legal empowerment - building Roma community knowledge of rights and legal processes	2
Community-based advocacy - developing local theory, building alliances and taking action to influence change at the local level	1
COVID-19 - addressing how the pandemic situation has affected Roma communities	1
Roma civil society organising - creation of Roma-centered organizations, movements, coalitions, etc. to advocate for their right	1

Annex 3. Scoping Review

Belén Soto-Ponce, Daniela E. Miranda, Ana Arenzana-Rodríguez, Ana Gutiérrez-Martínez, Tainara Paulon-Protásio, Pilar López-Parejo and Manuel García-Ramírez
Universidad de Sevilla - CESPYPD

A scoping review was carried out, following the protocols proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Four databases were included: PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, Scopus and PsycINFO. The search process lasted from March to August 2020. Firstly, a scoping review on Roma mental health was proposed. Due to the limited literature available on the subject, it was necessary to carry out a second search, including other racialized groups' mental health. Two sets of descriptors were used in combination (Table 1), in English and Spanish, based on the main objectives of the study.

Table 1. Search terms and combinations.

All databases		All databases
1.- Ethnicity terms		2.- Mental health terms
Ethnicity	AND	Mental health
Roma		Wellbeing
Gyps*		Salud mental
Gitan*		Bienestar

Quality of the literature was not established as an inclusion criterion, although we only considered empirical research. The relevance of the publications was considered more important than their quality. In this way, other peer-reviewed articles and gray literature were included in the scoping review, although they didn't match all the inclusion criteria. Furthermore, some of the articles that have been part of this review have been found through other means, such as by tracking the references included in the selected publications. Finally, articles with diverse age samples were included to gather all the available information on Roma or other ethnic mistreated groups' mental health (elderly, adults, children, women and men). Table 2 reflects the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the literature found.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the literature found.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Publications that provide specific data on racialized groups' mental health and determining factors, especially on Roma population, focusing on non-medical or psychosocial approaches	Publications related to physical health, genetic or biological variables or unrelated articles. Articles focused on migration variables were excluded.
Publication year: after January 1st, 2010	Publication year: before January 1st, 2010

Language: English and Spanish	Language: any language different than English or Spanish
Accessible publication	Not accessible publication
Empirical publications: quantitative, qualitative, mixed publications, and meta-analysis.	Not empirical publications: reports, book chapters, commentaries, editorials... Systematic and scoping reviews were also excluded.

The literature found was subjected to an exhaustive analysis by which the bibliography that is part of this review was chosen, following the principles of the flow approach developed by PRISMA (2015). Three screening processes were carried out: in the first screening, repeated publications were excluded. In the second, a title and abstract screening (TIAB) was carried out. In the third, a full-text screening was implemented (see figure 2). The dubious publications were discussed with other members of the research group, reaching an inter-judge agreement. Finally, the analysis of the finally selected literature was carried out using a data chart table that included the following variables, considered relevant for this work: authors and year of the publication, country in which the study was carried out, type of study and methodology used, characteristics of the sample, main objective, main results obtained, and limitations of the study. The publications included in this table have been ordered according to the year of publication, the most recent ones being in the first place (see table 3 and 4). This table is considered a good technique to synthesize and interpret qualitative data by filtering and classifying materials according to key aspects and themes (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005).

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram of scoping review screening process.

Through the bibliographic search, a total of 12,785 publications were found in the different databases mentioned above, as well as other documents found by other means that were included in the review as they were considered sufficiently relevant for this study. After the first screening, 5,048 publications that were repeated were excluded. From those, 218 publications were selected (1,71%), excluding 7,524 by the title and abstract screening. Subsequently, the 218 selected publications were subjected to a second screening, through which the final literature selection was made. In this last screening, 118 publications were excluded by reading the entire document, as it did not deal with the main topic of this study. Finally, in total, the articles included in this scoping review were 100 (0,8%) with a total of 12,690 publications excluded from the process.

Year	Publications
2020	10
2019	11
2018	7
2017	9
2016	11
2015	8
2014	6
2013	9
2012	12
2011	9
2010	8

Country	Publications
United States	69
Bulgaria, Czech Republic	5
United Kingdom, Serbia, Sweden	4
Spain, Romania, Australia, Norway	3
Albania, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia, Slovakia, Ireland	2
Belarus, Ukraine, Portugal, Croatia, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, Greece, South Africa, Canada, New Zealand	1

Figures 3 & 4. Year and origin of the final publications selected.

List of references included in the scoping review

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Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Chomynová, Kozák & Mravčík, 2020	Czech Republic	Cross-sectional quantitative study: National Survey on Substance Use 2016 (perceived health status, mental health, satisfaction with life, tobacco, alcohol and drug use, gambling, contact with counseling services, and socio-demographics.	546 respondents: Roma, permanent residents of the municipality and in regular contact with the outreach social worker.	1.Examine prevalence and patterns of substance use in Roma population in socially excluded localities. 2.Compare results to the prevalence of substance use in the general population.	1.The prevalence of tobacco smoking among Roma population was 2.7 times higher; daily alcohol use was comparable to the general population; prevalence of frequent binge drinking was 1.5 times higher among Roma; illicit substance use in Roma population was 2–6 times higher. 2.Unemployment was the most severity problem perceived by the 63.6% respondents followed by indebtedness (58.9%) and perceiving illicit drug use (51.9%). 46.9% perceived alcohol consumption as a very severe or severe problem, scoring much higher than other social problems (low quality of housing, loan-sharking, criminality, bad hygienic conditions or prostitution).	1.Only focused on Roma population and only those in contact with services. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias.
Gómez-Berrocal, Porras & Mata, 2020	Spain	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Scale of Psychological Wellbeing, Satisfaction with Life Scale, Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure and Measure of self-ingroup overlap.	229 spanish Roma from 18 to 89 years old.	Study the role of gender, age, educational level and group identification in well-being and satisfaction with life.	1.Only educational level is significantly related to satisfaction with life. Gender, age, educational level, and ethnic group are not related to psychological well-being. 2.Participants with the highest score in the ethnic identity variable report a higher level of well-being and satisfaction with life.	1. Age was not sufficiently controlled. 2. More exhaustive statistical analyzes are necessary, as well as the inclusion of other variables.
Vazsonyi, Liu, Beier & Blatny, 2020	Czech Republic	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Weinberger Adjustment Inventory	369 adolescents (64.8% Roma).	Analyze the association between perceived neighborhood variables and	1.Roma reported lower levels of SES, grades and academic aspirations. 2.Significant associations between background variables (age, sex, SES) and measures of adjustment in Roma and non-	1.Use of a convenience sample. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias.

Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		(depression, anxiety, self-esteem); Normative Deviance Scale (alcohol use, drug use, school misconduct); likert scales (neighborhood, academic variables).		health and wellbeing.	Roma: fear or concerns about neighborhood safety predicted depression, anxiety and low self-esteem, higher neighborhood cohesion predicted anxiety, density of acquaintanceship predicted alcohol and drug use, and more night social activities predicted alcohol use, school misconduct and lower grades. 3.The relationships were not moderated by ethnicity, although ethnicity (Roma) was positively associated with lower grades and academic aspirations.	3.Data collection was conducted using paper-and-pencil methods. 4.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Bosakova et al., 2019	Slovakia	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews, focus groups and direct observation.	122 Roma participants, 11 professionals, 10 public services professionals and 3 people from diverse fields.	Study the impact of increased employability on well-being and health.	1.Increased employability is related to an improvement in work ethics and habits, education and the acquisition of new skills, as well as an increase in self-confidence and social inclusion. 2.Regarding well-being, increased employability implies a more stable income, an improvement in precarious housing and a reduction in crime, as well as an improvement in hygiene, access to prevention and mental resilience.	1.No quantitative data is collected. 2.Some answers may be determined by social desirability.
Amador, Flecha & Sordé, 2018	Spain	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	9 Roma participants, some of them pastors	Determine how the Evangelical Church of Philadelphia prevents, stops drug addiction and supports mental health.	1.Protective factors towards detoxification are: anti-drug discourse, providing a supportive environment, creating new social relationships and becoming role models. 2.The protective factors towards mental health are: the promotion of well-being and reinforcement of self-esteem, the reevaluation of oneself with an emphasis on empowerment and the improvement of the feeling of belonging.	None mentioned.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Dimitrova et al., 2018	Albania, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Kosovo and Romania.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Utrecht Identity Commitment Management Scale (commitment, deep exploration and reconsideration of commitment); Satisfaction with Life Scale.	1,860 adolescents from 12 to 19 years old: 872 Roma.	Analyze the relationship between identity and life satisfaction.	1.Life satisfaction is consistently associated with high commitment, high deep exploration and low reconsideration of commitment in the field of educational identity. 2.The relationship between the different variables of the Utrecht Scale and life satisfaction differs between the different groups and countries. 3.Results could indicate that educational commitment is a stronger protective factor than relational commitment for the majority population, while for the Roma population, relational commitment is a stronger protective factor than educational commitment.	1.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population. 2.It does not include any qualitative measure.
Cvjetkovic, Jankovic, Bjegovic-Mikanovic, 2017	Serbia	Cross-sectional quantitative study: scale on subjective well-being.	2139 young people between 19 and 24 years old	1.Examine the relationship between social determinants and subjective well-being. 2.Analyze differences between Roma and non-Roma.	1.Roma reported being more unhappy and unsatisfied with life than non-Roma. Roma are more likely to report happiness and life satisfaction if they belong to the middle or upper class, while the probability that they report optimism is only higher for those of the upper class. 2.Non-Roma people living in rural areas report more unhappiness and life dissatisfaction than those living in urban areas. Non-Roma who have not had access to education or only have primary education are less likely to report satisfaction and optimism.	None mentioned.
Dimitrova et al., 2017	Bulgaria, Czech Republic,	Cross-sectional quantitative study: sociodemographic questionnaire;	1,221 adolescents: 632 Roma (194 from Bulgaria, 153 from Czech	1.Analyze how ethnic, national, familial and religious identity	1.Roma adolescents reported lower well-being and positive affect than the rest of the adolescents in Bulgaria and Kosovo, above all.	1.Context conditions were not assessed.

Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
	Kosovo and Romania.	four identity scales (Roma, national, familial, religious); Satisfaction with life scale and Positive Affect schedule.	Republic, 150 from Kosovo and 135 from Romania.	influence Roma well-being. 2.Outline areas of intervention to improve Roma well-being.	2.The Roma identity does not correlate positively with well-being in any of the countries, even negatively in two of the countries. 3.Familial and religious identity correlate positively with well-being in all Roma groups. Regarding national identity, no significant data was found in any country, indicating the marginal role that this type of identity plays in young Roma.	2.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population.
Lim, Cappa & Patton, 2017	Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia, Serbia and Ukraine.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: questionnaire on the domestic environment and demographic variables and on subjective wellbeing.	11,994 young people between 15 and 24 years old: 2,827 Roma (24%).	Analyze subjective wellbeing (life satisfaction, optimism and happiness) and its relationship with demographic factors.	There is no relationship between being Roma and life satisfaction or optimism. The Roma report being happier, although this data is not significant. Young Roma show levels of wellbeing similar to those of the general population, despite differences in living conditions.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Poor data analysis.
Heaslip, Hean & Parker, 2016	United Kingdom and Ireland	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	13 Roma travellers	Describe the experience of vulnerability of Roma travellers.	Six characteristics of vulnerability related to the situation of Roma travellers were found: 1) feeling defined and homogenized as a group; 2) pressured to conform to living in a certain way; 3) split in their identity; 4) loss of their cultural heritage; 5) feeling discriminated against, persecuted and threatened and 6) powerlessness, feeling that you have no voice.	1.Results could not be generalizable. 2.It was not focused on health issues.
Pereira et al., 2016	Portugal	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI); time	71 unemployed adults (31 Roma).	Analyze the differences in mental health between	1.Non-Roma obtained significantly higher scores than Roma in different areas: obsession-compulsion, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, anxiety, paranoid	1.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis.

Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		of unemployment.		unemployed Roma and non-Roma.	ideation, psychoticism, and in global severity. 2.Unemployment conditions have a much more negative impact on the mental health of non-Roma participants.	2.Results could not be generalizable.
Kamberi, Martinovic & Verkuyten, 2015	Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia and Macedonia.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Likert scales (subjective well-being, income, health, education, quality of housing, discrimination, ethnic identification).	11,997 participants: 8,399 Roma (70%), from twelve european countries.	Examine whether the Roma population has lower levels of subjective well-being than the rest of the population.	1.Roma have lower levels of health, a lower level of education, half of the income than non-Roma and perceive greater discrimination (the trend is the same in all countries although the strength of the associations differs). 2.Significantly, the Roma show a lower level of happiness and life satisfaction in the twelve countries.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Results are not generalizable to other countries. 3.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population.
Pappa et al., 2015	Greece	Cross-sectional quantitative study: SF-36 Health Survey.	1,068 Roma adults living in settlements.	1.Evaluate the HrQOL of Roma. 2.Analyze the factors that determine the HrQOL of Roma.	1.Roma men, the youngest and those with a partner report significantly higher scores on all scales compared to women, the elderly and the single people. 2.On the ‘vitality’ and ‘mental health’ scales, illiterate people have a lower level of health; high family income is associated with a higher level of health. 3.Having a stable home for the last 3 years increases the perception of health. Access to basic material resources (electricity, indoor drainage, and drinkable water) are associated with higher scores on most scales.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Results could not be generalizable to all the Roma groups.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Rogers, 2015	United Kingdom	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews, focus group and narrative conversations (2 discussion groups and 1 music, tales workshop) followed by nine individual narrative conversations.	8 English Travellers and 8 England Roma. All females between the ages of fifteen and mid-fifties.	1.Present emerging findings from on-going research studies exploring the bereavement experiences of Roma and Traveller families. 2.Considers resilience in relation to the bereavement experiences.	1.Close relationships between individuals promotes resilience and can provide barriers to exacerbated health risk. 2.A lack of intergenerational resilience and learnt responses to grief and bereavement are likely to result in the high levels of grief-related mental health problems. 3.The strong family attachments that should provide the balance in their lives, and which in many ways help them to develop resilience to the hardships of life are important in supporting them through physical and practical struggles, resilience in the face of bereavement (something which is difficult for anyone to cope with) appears to be compromised by the overriding cultural need to protect family members by asserting stoicism.	None mentioned.
Dimitrova et al., 2014	Bulgaria	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Bulgarian Mainstream Identity Scale, Roma Ethnic Identity Scale, Family Identity Scale, Religious Identity Scale and Satisfaction with Life Scale.	194 Roma adolescents (13 to 20 years old) and their mothers.	Investigate the relationship between ethnic, familial and religious identity and psychological well-being.	1.Familial identity is stronger compared to Roma, Bulgarian and religious identity for both adolescents and their mothers. 2.The four areas of identity are positively related to collective identity, which in turn is positively related to the wellbeing of adolescents and their mothers. The collective identity of mothers predicts the wellbeing of adolescents. 3.Roma identity and wellbeing are not related. The Bulgarian identity is indirectly related to well-being and happiness.	1.Results are not generalizable to other countries. 2.Only mothers were included. 3.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Alex & Lehti, 2013	Sweden	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	9 Sami women and 4 Roma women.	Analyze experiences of well-being and discomfort among	1.Factors that contribute to well-being: belonging to a healthy family, spirituality, cultural norms related to health promotion (daily contact with friends and family and	1. Small sample size of Roma women.

Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
				Sami and Roma women in Sweden.	living collectively) and having lived a life of their own. 2.Factors that contribute to discomfort: living subordinate to the majority society (those who see the Roma as inferior and without education), living in a hierarchical family (women subordinate to men) and living with tuberculosis.	2.The variable 'age' was not exhaustively controlled.
Dimitrova, 2013	Bulgaria	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Sociodemographic questionnaire; Bulgarian Mainstream Identity Scale; Familial Identity Scale, Religious Identity Scale; Satisfaction with Life Scale; Positive Affective Schedule.	606 participants with Roma (n= 207) and Bulgarian (n= 399) background. Age varied from 11 to 18 years.	Investigate links among domains of important for psychological wellbeing, during early and middle adolescence in Roma minority and Bulgarian majority groups.	1.Collective identity: Bulgarian adolescents show lower levels of religious identification than their Roma peers. No significant differences among the groups for Bulgarian and familial identity. 2.Collective identity x wellbeing: Roma youth scoring significantly lower on satisfaction with life. No significant differences between Roma and Bulgarian groups were found for positive affect. 3.Collective identity has the same relationship with wellbeing in the two ethnic groups; Bulgarian, familial, and religious identity were positively and significantly related to wellbeing, irrespective of ethnic group membership.	1.Impact of discrimination and segregation assessed indirectly. 2.Longitudinal design would be more appropriate. 3.Lack of other important demographic information, specifically for the Roma group. 4.Self-report measures.
McGorrian, Hamid, Fitzpatrick, Daly, Malone & Kelleher, 2013	Ireland	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (HrQOL); likert scale (self-rated health, social support);	8,492 families.	Examine the associations between sociodemographic and lifestyle factors with poor mental health in Irish Travellers.	1. Travellers experience discrimination and bereavement, which negatively influence their mental health. 2. The importance of contextualising mental health symptomatology and using systematic methods of measurement. 3. Clear implications for policy and may be relevant to other indigenous ethnic groups worldwide, that face similar circumstances.	1.Using self-reported measures, without clinical or cultural validation, may be a cause of bias. 2.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.

Table 3. Data chart of the main obtained results on Romani communities.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		experience of discrimination scale.				
Hassler & Eklund, 2012	Sweden	Cross-sectional quantitative study: short-form Health Survey (physical and mental component) and the Antonovsky's Sense of Coherence Scale.	99 Roma adults	Investigate the relationship between the sense of coherence and self-reported health.	1. The Roma show lower scores in both physical and mental health, being these significantly different than the non-Roma Swedish population. 2. The sense of coherence was significantly lower in the Roma population; furthermore, it correlates significantly with mental and physical health.	1. Questionnaires based on a western way of life being not sufficiently valid for Roma. 2. Acces difficulties to these populations.
Janevic, Jankovic & Bradley, 2012	Serbia	Cross-sectional quantitative study.	14,313 participants, 267 Roma (1,9%).	Analyze differences in self-perceived health between Roma and non-Roma.	1. Significant differences between Roma and non-Roma: the Roma reported lower educational level, higher poverty level and higher unemployment rate. 2. Roma are more than twice as likely to report worse health than non-Roma. 3. Roma women are at higher risk of experiencing poor health.	1. The meaning of health may be different for each group. 2. The results cannot be generalized to other populations. 3. Underestimation of the Roma sample.
Carrasco-Garrido, De Andrés, Hernández Barrera, Jiménez-Trujillo & Jiménez-García, 2010	Spain	Cross-sectional quantitative study, data from the National Health Survey in Spain.	1,581 women (Roma).	spanish (527 Describe the health status of Roma women in Spain.	1. Roma women are more likely to suffer from certain health problems such as obesity, depression or migraines. 2. In terms of lifestyles, Roma women report significantly higher levels of alcohol consumption than non-Roma women and do less physical exercise, although they smoke less. 3. Roma women have a poorer perception of their health, but the percentage of women who attend health services is not significantly higher. Roma consume less medication but self-medicate more.	1. Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 2. Other important variables have not been included in the analysis.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Van Cleemput, 2010	United Kingdom	Cross-sectional qualitative study: structured interviews about their beliefs, attitudes and experiences regarding access and use of health services..	27 gypsies and travellers.	Explore the long-term impact on health of processes of historical exclusion.	1.Despite reporting multiple health problems, Roma travellers did not consider themselves to have poor health. However, they report, for example, suffering depression conditions which they prefer to face alone rather than receiving medical assistance. 2. Their experience with racism in society has significant adverse effects on the mental health of these communities, fueling the general distrust towards all sectors of the population, especially towards health professionals: the interviewees highlight the cultural insensitivity of these professionals.	None mentioned.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Allende González-Velázquez, Shackelford, Keller, Vinney & Drake, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: BBC Wellbeing Scale; Psychological Empowerment Scale; Desirability of Control Scale; General Self-efficacy Scale; Hopefulness Measure; Personal Mastery Measure; Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure.	145 participants were rising American high school seniors between the ages of 15 and 20 who had been accepted into the 2018 Leadership, Education and Development (LEAD) cohort.	1.Explores how teenagers react to the film Black Panther, especially in relation to strength of ethnic identification and identification with the film's hero. 2.Explore how those related to empowerment and wellbeing.	1.Watching Black Panther increased empowerment but not wellbeing, and there was no interaction with ethnicity. 2.The film's effect on wellbeing was significant for Black/AA and AsA participants only and the film's effect on empowerment was significant for Black/AA participants only. 3.The film was particularly empowering for Black AA youth.	None mentioned.
Baiden, LaBrenz, Asiedua-Baiden & Muehlenkamp, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: binary variables (suicidal ideation and suicide attempt; bullying victimization, forced sexual intercourse, depression, cigarette smoking, alcohol and cannabis use, misuse of prescription pain	13,697 adolescents (14–18 years old): 5,932 White (43.3%); 2,627 Black or AA (19.2%); 3,487 Hispanic/Latino (25.4%); 228 American Indian/Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander (AI/NH/PI) (1.7%); 1,423 other (10.4%).	Examine the intersection of sexual orientation and race/ethnicity on suicidal ideation and suicide attempt.	1.Suicidal ideation: Black/AA and Hispanics had lower odds, while AI/NH/PI had higher odds than Whites. Factors associated with suicidal ideation were gender (female had more odds of reporting suicide behaviors), history of forced sexual intercourse, bullying, depression, cigarette smoking, misuse of prescription pain medicine, and use of illicit drugs. 2.Suicide attempts: Black/AA, Hispanic, AI/NH/PI, or "other" had higher odds. Hispanic lesbian/gay adolescents had higher odds of making a suicide attempt, followed by Black/AA bisexual adolescents and AI/NH/PI bisexual adolescents. Factors associated with	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis. 3.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		medicine, illicit drug use); sexual orientation and race/ethnicity			suicide attempt; bullying, cyberbullying, depression, cigarette, cannabis or illicit drugs use, misused prescription pain medicine, or having a history of forced sexual intercourse.	
Bergeron, De La Cruz, Gould, Yan Liu & Levanon Seligson, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Experiences of Discrimination survey; HrQOL and social relationships questions; material hardship, sex, age, nativity and socio-economic factors.	2335 respondents: 925 Whites (34,4%), 513 Blacks (22,2%), 583 Latinos (27,5%), 229 Asian/Pacific Islander (13,4%), 85 other (2,4%)	1.Describe the relationships between racial discrimination and HrQOL among diverse racial/ethnic groups. 2.Explore if social relationships moderate this relation.	1.Racial discrimination: Blacks, Asian/Pis and Latinos more frequently reported these experiences (and in 3 or more domains) compared with whites. 2.Significant associations were found between racial discrimination and self-rated poor physical health, poor mental health, and limitations by poor physical and mental health. The odds of reporting poor health was higher among whites who experienced racial discrimination in 3 or more domains. Racial discrimination and poor mental health and limitations were associated in Latinos. Asian/Pis who experienced racial discrimination in less than 3 domains, reported better physical health. 3.Social relationships moderated the interaction between racial discrimination and mental health and limitations.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Limited assessment of social relationships. Also, personality traits, sociocultural factors or identity intersections were not measured. 3.Ethnic subgroups were not specified.
Chomynová, Kozák & Mravčík, 2020	Czech Republic	Cross-sectional quantitative study: National Survey on Substance Use 2016 (perceived health status, mental health, satisfaction with	546 respondents: Roma, permanent residents of the municipality and in regular contact with the outreach social worker.	1.Examine prevalence and patterns of substance use in Roma population in socially excluded localities.	1.The prevalence of tobacco smoking among Roma population was 2.7 times higher; daily alcohol use was comparable to the general population; prevalence of frequent binge drinking was 1.5 times higher among Roma; illicit substance use in Roma population was 2–6 times higher. 2.Unemployment was the most severity problem perceived by the 63.6%	1.Only focused on Roma population and only those in contact with services. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		life, tobacco, alcohol and drug use, gambling, contact with counseling services, and socio-demographics.		2.Compare results to the prevalence of substance use in the general population.	respondents followed by indebtedness (58.9%) and perceiving illicit drug use (51.9%). 46.9% perceived alcohol consumption as a very severe or severe problem, scoring much higher than other social problems (low quality of housing, loan-sharking, criminality, bad hygienic conditions or prostitution).	
Gómez-Berrocal, Porras & Mata, 2020	Spain	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Scale of Psychological Wellbeing, Satisfaction with Life Scale, Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure and Measure of self-ingroup overlap.	229 spanish Roma from 18 to 89 years old.	Study the role of gender, age, educational level and group identification in well-being and satisfaction with life.	1.Only educational level is significantly related to satisfaction with life. Gender, age, educational level, and ethnic group are not related to psychological well-being. 2.Participants with the highest score in the ethnic identity variable report a higher level of well-being and satisfaction with life.	1. Age was not sufficiently controlled. 2. More exhaustive statistical analyzes are necessary, as well as the inclusion of other variables.
Greene, Jackson & Dean, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: binge drinking, heavy alcohol use; ethnicity, sexual identity and intersectionality disparities.	21,024 participants who identified as women.	Examine disparities in excessive alcohol use at the intersection of race-ethnicity and sexual identity for non-Hispanic Black and Hispanic sexual minority women.	Black and Hispanic sexual minority women reported the highest prevalence of binge drinking (45.4% and 43.4%, respectively). The joint disparity in binge drinking between Black sexual minority women and White heterosexual women was 21.2%, and the excess intersectional disparity was 17.7%.	None mentioned

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Rose, Hope, Thurman, Forrester & Rose, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Likert scales (non-organizational religious involvement, life satisfaction); RSES; Pearlin's Mastery Scale; John Henryism scale (active coping); Cohen's perceived stress scale; CES-D.	1,119 youths: 777 AAs and 342 CBs.	Explore the influence of non-organizational religious involvement (NRI) on psychosocial well-being.	1.NRI was significantly correlated with life satisfaction, self-esteem and coping for AA, while for CB it was significantly correlated with life satisfaction and coping. 2.There was no statistically significant difference in the association between NRI and each outcome by ethnicity. 3.NRI was significantly related to life satisfaction after controlling for the other variables (every 1-point increase in NRI score was associated with a 38% increase in odds of being more satisfied). Higher levels of NRI were significantly associated with higher levels of self-esteem. NRI was significantly associated with coping. 4.NRI was a statistically significant predictor of depressive symptoms.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences, as well as the ability to explore the long-term impact of NRI on wellbeing. 3.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 4.Exploring within group differences was not possible. 5.Results are not generalizable to other ethnic groups.
Sahdra et al., 2020	Australia	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Likert scales (felt discrimination, subjective well-being); General Health Questionnaire; Student Social Support Scale, close friend nominations.	High school students from three ethnically diverse public schools: 46% white; 20% indigenous; 34% other minorities.	Empirically examine the effects of the framework related to discrimination in overlapping friendship groups of young people of various ethnicities.	1.Evidence is provided for a framework effect involving discrimination. 2.The relative position of individuals in their communities of friends with high group discrimination reliably predicted the levels of well-being of individuals, regardless of their ethnicity. 3.The importance of identifying overlapping friendship communities is highlighted in order to understand the dynamics of discrimination and the well-being of ethnically diverse youth.	1.Not focused on how marginalized they felt compared to their friends. 2.Cross-sectional data rather than longitudinal assessments. 3.Focus on quantity rather than quality of friendship.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Schmitz, Robinson, Tabler, Welch y Rafaqut, 2020	United States	Cross-sectional study of mixed methods: in-depth, face-to-face interview (LGBTQ+, racial/ethnic identities and health) and short demographic questionnaire.	41 participants who are 18-26 years old and self-identify as LGTBQ, as well as being Latino.	Examine subjective perceptions of marginalization, stigma, and mental health using an intersectional minority stress perspective.	1.Demonstrates the complexity of the realities experienced by Latino/LGBTQ+ young adults in how perceived structural stigma shapes mental health challenges. These findings speak to emergency research that underscores the importance of intersectional frameworks in analyzing the health of LGBTQ+ youth of color. 2.It highlights how the intersection of social status can dynamically shape health inequalities, making a "one size fits all" approach to understanding how stigma affects health outcomes inadequate.	1.Convenience sampling methods-restricted sampling frame. 2.They did not examine the processes of interpersonal racism. 3.Cross-sectional nature of the data.
Vazsonyi, Liu, Beier & Blatny, 2020	Czech Republic	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Weinberger Adjustment Inventory (depression, anxiety, self-esteem); Normative Deviance Scale (alcohol use, drug use, school misconduct); likert scales (neighborhood, academic variables).	369 adolescents (64.8% Roma).	Analyze the association between perceived neighborhood variables and health and wellbeing.	1.Roma reported lower levels of SES, grades and academic aspirations. 2.Significant associations between background variables (age, sex, SES) and measures of adjustment in Roma and non-Roma: fear or concerns about neighborhood safety predicted depression, anxiety and low self-esteem, higher neighborhood cohesion predicted anxiety, density of acquaintanceship predicted alcohol and drug use, and more night social activities predicted alcohol use, school misconduct and lower grades. 3.The relationships were not moderated by ethnicity, although ethnicity (Roma) was positively associated with lower grades and academic aspirations.	1.Use of a convenience sample. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 3.Data collection was conducted using paper-and-pencil methods. 4.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Bosakova et al., 2019	Slovakia	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured	122 participants , 11 professionals, 10 Roma	Study the impact of increased employability on	1.Increased employability is related to an improvement in work ethics and habits, education and the acquisition of new skills,	1.No quantitative data is collected.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		interviews, focus groups and direct observation.	public services professionals and 3 people from diverse fields.	well-being and health.	as well as an increase in self-confidence and social inclusion. 2.Regarding well-being, increased employability implies a more stable income, an improvement in precarious housing and a reduction in crime, as well as an improvement in hygiene, access to prevention and mental resilience.	2.Some answers may be determined by social desirability.
Feinstein, Turner, Beach, Korpak & Phillips, 2019	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Binary questions (sadness/hopelessness and suicidal ideation, substance use, bullying); sexual orientation, ethnicity, sex, age.	18,515 bisexual youth: 40.3% White, 17.0% Black, 32.1% Hispanic, and 10.7% other races.	1.Examine racial/ethnic differences in mental health and substance use among bisexual youth. 2.Analyze racial/ethnic differences in bullying and its relationship with mental health.	1.Blacks and Hispanics were less likely to report bullying than Whites. Blacks were less likely to report sadness/ hopelessness, suicidal ideation, cigarette, marijuana, illicit drug use and binge drinking than Whites. Black 2.Compared with Blacks, Hispanics were more likely to report sadness/hopelessness, suicidal ideation, cigarette use, and other illicit drug use.	1.Overrepresentation of bisexual female youth, and other ethnic groups were not considered. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 3.Measures did not assess racial discrimination.
Forster, Rogers, Benjamin, Grigsby, Lust & Eisenberg, 2019	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: American College Health Association-National College Health Assessment; College Student Health Survey; Adverse Childhood Experiences	7,148 students, between 18 and 27 years old: 50% Non-Hispanic White; the rest: Hispanic, AA/Black, Asian Pacific Islanders, multiracial.	1.Estimate the prevalence of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) and substance use. 2.Investigate ethnic differences in the relationship between ACE and substance use.	1.Increases in ACE were associated with higher odds of using almost all substances, but there were ethnic differences: non-ACE-exposed AA/Black students had relatively low probability of binge drinking, as ACE increased, they had the highest probability of binge drinking relative to their peers; Hispanics, who had similar alcohol use patterns as Whites, as ACE increased the odds of binge drinking also exceeded that of their White peers; Asian Pacific Islander students, who had the lowest overall prevalence of marijuana use and one of the lowest for tobacco use,	1.Highest risk students did not participate: Limited generalizability. 2. Cross-sectional data do not support causal conclusions. 3. Different sample size in each ethnic group and no difference across subgroups. 4.Measures of variables limited.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		(ACE) and substance use.			as ACE increased however, the probability of using marijuana and tobacco exceeded that of any other group. 2.Associations between accumulated ACE and alcohol use, illicit drug use, and polysubstance use did not vary across ethnicity categories.	
Holley, Oh & Thomas, 2019	United States	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews about supports and discrimination from multiple sources.	20 people with mental health conditions (MHC) or members of their families: 12 LGB, 15 people of color and 7 LGB of color.	Explore how discriminatory experiences relate to the intersection of race-ethnicity, sexuality and mental health status.	1.Mental Illness Discrimination in Communities of Color: participants expressed lack of information in their communities (“ <i>MHC don’t exist</i> ” and lack of education about MHC); stereotypes (“ <i>MHC make you incompetent, invalid</i> ”); looking down on (being laughed at); blame, shame, and silence; and identity intersections affect discrimination. 2.Supports Within Communities of Color: some reported no community support, while the elder from Indigenous communities were supportive. 3.Benefits of peer-run programs and family-run programs: programs were reported to entail enjoyable activities, empathy due to shared experiences, freedom to talk and humanization. 4.Programs for people of color: participants expressed that ethnic community-specific programs are needed; sharing cultures and experiences would be beneficial.	1.Participants involved in formal mental health programs. 2. The temporal context of the interviews is important. 3.Possible underreportation of experiences of discrimination.
Polanco-Roman, Angling, Miranda & Jeglic, 2019	United States	A cross-sectional quantitative study: General Ethnic	1,344 emerging adults, U.S.-born (76%): 46% Hispanic/Latino,	1.Identify potential explanatory factors in the	1.Frequent experiences of racial/ethnic discrimination may increase risk of traumatic stress and depressive symptoms, which may, in turn, increase risk of	1.Sample consists of predominantly female college students.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		Discrimination Scale; Impact of Events Scale; Beck Depression Inventory; Suicidal Behaviors Questionnaire.	20% non-Hispanic White, 18% non-Hispanic Black, 12% Asian, and 4% identified as other.	relation between racial/ethnic discrimination and suicide-related risk. 2.Examine if this relation varied by race/ethnicity and gender.	suicidal thoughts, particularly in young women. 2.No racial/ethnic difference was evident in this relation. 3.An approach to reducing suicide-related risk in racial/ethnic minority young women should consider racial/ethnic discrimination as a potential source of psychological distress.	2.It is possible that suicide-related risk is underestimated among racial/ethnic minority students.
Rose et al., 2019	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: National Survey of American Life-Adolescent.	1,170 young people between 13 and 17 years of age: 810 AA (69%) and 360 CB (31%).	1.Identify patterns of connection to key developmental environments. 2.Explore how they are associated with wellbeing. 3.Examine if social-welfare connections differ by ethnicity or gender.	1.This study elucidates the critical importance of considering multiple social environments as targets for intervention. School and community professionals can design individual, small group, gender-specific, or even larger-scale, culturally relevant strategies that enhance multiple aspects of connection in an effort to improve the psychosocial well-being of black youth. 2.These findings add to the existing literature on positive adolescent and youth development and contribute to a better understanding of the importance of social environments among subgroups of adolescents, resulting in a more complete picture of the factors supporting well-being throughout adolescence.	1.Cross-sectional design, it is not possible to infer causality. 2.Use of existing data limits the representation of the constructs and some of the measures of the study had little reliability. 3.Age was not assessed.
Sánchez, Vandewater & Hamilton, 2019	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Marianismo beliefs scale; Multigroup Ethnic identity	277 low-income Mexican American early adolescent girls.	Explore relations between five pillars of marianismo, ethnic identity, mental health and substance use	Familismo, virtuous/chaste, and spiritual marianismo gender role attitudes were predictive of stronger ethnic identity; conversely, self-silencing marianismo attitudes were predictive of weaker ethnic identity. Results of hierarchical logistic regressions revealed that both virtuous/chaste	1.Correlational and cross-sectional study, (not able to stablish direction). 2.Dichotomous measure of substance abuse.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		measure (MEIM); Youth Risk Behavior Survey (substance use behaviors); demographics.		among low-income early adolescents.	marianismo gender role attitudes and mental health (low rates of psychological distress) were inversely linked with substance use; furthermore, they had a combined link that was related to even lower rates of substance use among participants. ethnic identity did not have a direct or moderating effect on substance use.	
Swann, Stephens, Newcomb & Whitton, 2019	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Experiences of overt sexual and gender minority victimization Scale; Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory; Brief Perceived Ethnic Discrimination Questionnaire; Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information system; Alcohol/Cannabis Use Disorders Identification Test.	Community-based sample of female assigned at birth (FAB) and sexual and gender minority (SGM) who also identified as racial/ethnic minorities: 167 (47.4%) Black/AA, 119 Hispanic/Latinx (33.8%), 37 multiracial (10.5%), 24 Asian/Pacific Islander (6.8%), and 5 identified as “other” (1.4%).	Assess the negative effects of both SGM and race-based enacted stigma on mental health and substance use problems in SGM of color.	1.Enacted stigma based on both race/ethnicity and SGM status were significant predictors of mental health outcomes and alcohol-related problems within the same model: both contributed to poorer health. 2.Across all mental health and substance use outcomes, there was no evidence of an interaction between the two types of enacted stigma: one form of enacted stigma did not become worse in the presence of the other, but FAB SGM who experienced both still experienced the worst outcomes. 3.SGM-based microaggressions and racial discrimination were associated with symptoms of depression and anxiety, and SGM-based victimization and racial discrimination were associated with more alcohol-related problems. 4.Marijuana-related problems were best explained by enacted stigma based on race/ethnicity only. 5.Results did not support a resilience framework.	1.SGM and race/ethnicity- stigma measured as separate unidimensional predictors. 2.Differences between the specific form of enacted stigma assessed. 3.Participants who identified as gender minorities may have responded to the SGM victimization measure differently. 4.Cross-sectional data, 5.Only included female assigned at birth SGM.

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Velez, Polihronakis, Watson & Cox, 2019	United States	Cross sectional quantitative: Heterosexist Harassment, Rejection and Discrimination Scale; General Ethnic Discrimination Scale; Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual Identity Scale; Collective Self-esteem Scale; Hopkins Symptom Checklist-21; Psychological Wellbeing Scale.	318 sexual minority and racial or ethnic minority participants: 92 (29%) Hispanic or Latino/a American; 73 (23%) Biracial or Multiracial; 66 (21%) Asian or AsA; 43 (14%) African, AA, or Black; 44 (8%) other racial and/or ethnic identity.	Provide additional examinations of the additive and multiplicative approaches to understanding the roles of multiple systems of oppression—heterosexism and racism—in the lives and mental health of sexual minority People of Color.	1.Heterosexist/racist discrimination and internalized heterosexism/racism yielded positive correlations with psychological distress and negative correlations with psychological well-being. 2.Heterosexist discrimination and internalized racism contributed to psychological distress. Well-being was predicted only by internalized heterosexism/ racism. 3.Heterosexist discrimination/racist discrimination were strongly correlated. Internalized heterosexism/racism were moderately correlated. 4.Internalized racism interacted with both heterosexist discrimination (a cross-oppression interaction) and racist discrimination (a same-oppression interaction) in relation to psychological distress and well-being.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Forms of oppression are assumed to be separate. 3.Given the sample size, inability to explore potential differences across the racial and/or ethnic groups.
Wang et al., 2019	United States, Australia	Systematic revision and meta-analysis.	102 studies with 803 effect sizes and 27,221 participants.	1.Elucidate the associations between ethnic-racial socialization and psychosocial outcomes. 2.Investigate the moderating role of individual characteristics, research design, and reporter of ethnic-racial socialization.	1.Ethnic-racial socialization was positively, associated with self-perceptions (larger during early adolescence), interpersonal relationship quality, and internalizing behavior. 2.Cultural socialization exhibited more consistently associations with multiple facets of psychosocial well-being: positive relations with self-perceptions and interpersonal relationship quality; negative link with externalizing behaviors. 3.Ethnic-racial socialization’s connection to psychosocial outcomes varied by the subtype that parents used, the developmental stage and race/ethnicity of	1.Associations are correlational not causal. 2.It was not tested the prospective mechanisms underlying the link between ethnic-racial socialization and psychosocial development.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
					the target child, and the reporter of ethnic-racial socialization. Ethnic-racial socialization's positive association with self-perceptions was strongest in early adolescence and among AA youth.	
Yang & Park, 2019	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: CES-D; social support (positive spousal/friends/relatives support); informal/formal social integration; demographics (including number of recent negative events).	In wave 1 (1986) 3,617 adults; in wave 2 (1989) 2,867 participants; in wave 3 (1994), 2,562 adults; in wave 4 (2001/2002), 1,787 people; and in wave 5 (2011), 1,427 respondents. Oversampling of black people.	Analyze how sources of social support (spouse and friend/relative) and types of social integration (informal/formal) explain black-white and Hispanic-white disparities in depression.	1.Strong social support and high social integration are negatively associated with depression and that the patterns of social support and integration vary by race/ethnicity. 2.The results of hybrid models show that social support from one's spouse and friend/relative account for over 25 percent of the black-white disparity, whereas formal social integration including religious groups widens the black-white differential by roughly 10 percent. 3.However, Hispanic-white disparities in depression are mostly a result of the difference in SES. The change in spousal support is the most powerful predictor for the change in depression across race/ethnicity groups.	1.Neighborhood data was not included. 2.Differences in instruments to assess social support complicates comparability. 3.It remains unknown whether social support and integration are potential explanations for this phenomenon.
Amador, Flecha & Sordé, 2018	Spain	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	9 Roma participants, some of them pastors	Determine how the Evangelical Church of Philadelphia prevents, stops drug addiction and supports mental health.	1.Protective factors towards detoxification are: anti-drug discourse, providing a supportive environment, creating new social relationships and becoming role models. 2.The protective factors towards mental health are: the promotion of well-being and reinforcement of self-esteem, the reevaluation of oneself with an emphasis on empowerment and the improvement of the feeling of belonging.	None mentioned.

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Assari, Lapeyrouse & Neighbors, 2018	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: household income; self-rated mental health (single item).	881 adults: 92 Blacks and 782 Whites.	Black–White comparison of the association between household income and self-rated mental health (SRMH).	1.Higher household income was associated with better SRMH, net of covariates. 2.An interaction was found between race/ethnicity and household income on SRMH, suggesting a smaller, or nonexistent, protective effect for Blacks compared to Whites. 3. In race/ethnicity-stratified models, higher household income was associated with better SRMH for Whites but not Blacks.	1.Limited to a sample with landlines and local cellphones, and the study excluded non-English speakers. 2.Causal associations were not established. 3.Single-item measure no measured cofounders.
Dimitrova et al., 2018	Albania, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Kosovo and Romania.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Utrecht Identity Commitment Management Scale (commitment, deep exploration and reconsideration of commitment); Satisfaction with Life Scale.	1,860 adolescents from 12 to 19 years old: 872 Roma.	Analyze the relationship between identity and life satisfaction.	1.Life satisfaction is consistently associated with high commitment, high deep exploration and low reconsideration of commitment in the field of educational identity. 2.The relationship between the different variables of the Utrecht Scale and life satisfaction differs between the different groups and countries. 3.Results could indicate that educational commitment is a stronger protective factor than relational commitment for the majority population, while for the Roma population, relational commitment is a stronger protective factor than educational commitment.	1.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population. 2.It does not include any qualitative measure.
Kim, Bassett, Takahashi & Voisin, 2018	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: RSES; Brief Symptom Inventory –18 (mental health); delinquent	638 low-income AA adolescents; ages of 13–24 years.	Examine whether high levels of self-esteem are associated with better behavioral health factors.	Being female and LGBTQ were associated with negative mental health factors. Males who reported higher self-esteem were less likely to be involved in delinquent behaviors, less likely to report negative mental health factors and less likely to report having survival sex than female	Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.

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		behaviors, substance use, school engagement, sexual behaviour, demographics.			counterparts. Participants reporting higher self-esteem were more likely to report higher student-teacher connectedness and school bonding, less likely to report drug use, less negative mental health factors and lower rates of all sexual risk behaviors.	
Krause, Pargament, Hill & Ironson, 2018	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Landmark Spirituality and Health Survey (physical illness, anxiety, happiness, spiritual struggles).	3,010 respondents of Black, White and Hispanics backgrounds.	1.Assess variations in spiritual struggles, health and wellbeing. 2.Examine differential-exposure perspective and the differential-impact perspective.	With respect to differential exposure, the data suggest that Blacks tend to experience more spiritual struggles than either Whites or Hispanics. Blacks encounter more spiritual struggles than members of the other racial/ethnic groups, but they tend to have fewer symptoms of physical illness, less anxiety, and more happiness than either Whites or Hispanics.	1.Cross sectional nature. 2.It is not possible to tell if spiritual struggles erode health or if physical health problems create new spiritual struggles.
Mitchel et al., 2018	United States	Transversal study of mixed methods: rated perceptions of typicality; open-ended prompts; Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure; Erikson Psychosocial Stage Inventory; CES-D; RSES.	74 students from 3 universities: 5% black, 30% Asian, 10% Latino, 40% white, 11% multiracial, 1% Native American and 4% other ethnicity.	Explore one aspect of the content of ethnic-racial identity (ERIs), namely, ethno-racial typicalness, or the degree and nature of perceived similarity that individuals feel in relation to their ethno-racial group.	1.Individuals judged their typical and atypical ethnic group by focusing on skin color, hair, facial features; values related to family, achievement and religion-spirituality; and behaviors related to the arts-media, sports, time spent with others and food. 2.It was shown that most individuals felt typical of their ethnic group and, more importantly, that the level of perceived typicality was inversely related to measures of ethnic identity and well-being. 3.Participants differed in their feeling of being typical because of ethnic and racial group identifications.	1.No causal inference is possible from the study. 2.Only university students were included, which limits generalization.

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Walton, 2018	United States	Cross-sectional, mixed methods: WMH-CIDI; Sense of community Index; race, home-ownership and neighborhood tenure; in depth-interviews.	243 participants in the surveys; 60 responded the interviews in neighborhood 1, while 29 did so in neighborhood 2.	1.Explore how social resources are distributed within diverse neighborhoods. 2.Analyze the existence and nature of relationships among sense of community and mental health.	1.Social goods are not equitably distributed among residents in diverse neighborhoods. 2.Whites and homeowners have more access to the mental health benefits of sense of community (through the perception of greater and more effective mutual influence) than blacks and renters. 3.Residents with a different privileged social status—long neighborhood tenure—do not experience any mental health benefits from feelings of membership and emotional connection to neighbors. Mutual influence matters for mental health the most. 4.Resident narratives reveal how the ability to influence others and be influenced by others are important aspects beneficial for mental health status. When one feels marginalized, lacking influence over others, one's community becomes an unpredictable, insecure place, serving to increase vulnerability to stressors.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Immigrants or actual ethnicity in some locations could not be totally representative.
Assari, Moghani & Caldwell, 2017	United States	Cross sectional quantitative study: Everyday Discrimination Scale; questions on suicidal ideation; age, gender, ethnicity, SES.	1,170 Black adolescents, including 810 AAs and 360 CB.	1.Investigated the effects of discrimination, ethnicity, gender, and SES on suicidal ideation. 2.Test gender and ethnic differences.	1.CBs had a higher median income than AAs AAs and CBs reported similar levels of discrimination. Boys reported significantly higher levels of discrimination. 2.AAs and CBs did not differ in suicidal ideation. Suicidal ideation was more common among girls. 3.Higher perceived discrimination was associated with higher odds of suicidal ideation. This association was significant above and beyond age, ethnicity, gender,	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Sample size was not identical across gender and ethnic groups. 3.Single-item measures; other important variables have not been included in the analysis.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
Benner & Wang, 2017	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Adolescent Discrimination Distress Index; Cross-Ethnic friendships; Likert scales (loneliness); Children's Depressive Inventory; Perceived Social Norms for Schoolwork and Achievement (school belonging); Effective School Battery (school engagement).	252 eighth-grade students: 85% Latino, 11% AA, and 5% other (i.e., biracial, AsA, White).	Examine the moderating role of cross-ethnic friendships and close friends' experiences of discrimination in the link between adolescents' perceptions of discrimination and wellbeing.	SES. 1.49% of adolescents identified at least one cross-ethnic friend. Adolescent with no cross-ethnic friendships reported less peer discrimination than adolescents with at least one cross-ethnic friendship. 2. Adolescents reporting more peer-perpetrated discrimination were lonelier and more depressed, whereas adolescents reporting more teacher-perpetrated discrimination were less engaged in school and had lower school belonging. 3. Significant interaction between adolescents' perceptions of peer-perpetrated discrimination and their cross-ethnic friendships. 4. Friends' perceptions of peer-perpetrated racial/ethnic discrimination also moderated the effects of students' perceptions of peer-perpetrated discrimination and their feelings of school belonging.	1. Predominantly Latino students limiting the generalizability of our findings. 2. Cannot determine whether the pattern of effects unfold consistently across different racial/ethnic Groups.
Bosma, Orozco, Barriga, Rosas-Lee & Sieving, 2017	United States	Cross-sectional qualitative analysis: 10 focus groups with youth and 4 with parents, community-university analysis of data.	109 youth participants between 14 and 22 years of age.	Obtain contextual insights from youth and parents regarding social challenges faced by Latino youth as well as protective factors that contribute to their resilience.	1. Economic stability was noted as important by both parents and youth as necessary to actively participate in their children's lives. 2. Latinos face discrimination and often must overcome stereotypes/racism in their daily lives at work/school and in daily interactions. 3. Limits related to immigration status can place great uncertainty and stress on youth	Convenience sample may not be generalizable to Latino youth and parents in other settings.

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					and families and make achieving certain goals. 4.Resilient elements included: skills (intellectual, practical life, self-regulation), parental support for making healthy decisions, positive self-perception and self-efficacy, self-respect and confidence, determination and motivation, faith, hope and sense of purpose, positive attachment and relationship parents and caring adults, prosocial friends, bonds to schools, safe neighborhood environment and cultural aspects.	
Cvjetkovic, Jankovic, Bjegovic-Mikanovic, 2017	Serbia	Cross-sectional quantitative study: scale on subjective well-being.	2139 young people between 19 and 24 years old	1.Examine the relationship between social determinants and subjective well-being. 2.Analyze differences between Roma and non-Roma.	1.Roma reported being more unhappy and unsatisfied with life than non-Roma. Roma are more likely to report happiness and life satisfaction if they belong to the middle or upper class, while the probability that they report optimism is only higher for those of the upper class. 2.Non-Roma people living in rural areas report more unhappiness and life dissatisfaction than those living in urban areas. Non-Roma who have not had access to education or only have primary education are less likely to report satisfaction and optimism.	None mentioned.
Dill, 2017	United States	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews (personal goals, involvement in youth-serving	25 youth between 12-20 years old: 80% AA (n=20), 20% Latina/o/x (n=5).	Examine spirituality as personal resource and agentic strategy by which AA youth cope against individual-	1.Use of Praying to cope with personal incidences (murders, shooting, etc.) and to ask for protection and for safety in their neighborhoods. God protects them and keeps them safe, intangible sense of protection.	None mentioned.

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		organization (EOYDC), living experiences, perceptions of neighborhood change, relationships with and leveragability of networks).		and neighborhood-level stressors in their lives.	2.Faith talk: beliefs, practices, and rituals (other than praying) related to spirituality in order to cope: leaving it “in God’s hands: help to have a more positive outlook on the situations. Acts of service as a direct extension of their faith: importance of financial giving as part of their faith, which also contributes to the overall well-being of their neighborhoods. spirituality serves as an internal coping mechanism when external supports fail	
Dimitrova et al., 2017	Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Kosovo and Romania.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: sociodemographic questionnaire; four identity scales (Roma, national, familial, religious); Satisfaction with life scale and Positive Affect schedule.	1,221 adolescents: 632 Roma (194 from Bulgaria, 153 from Czech Republic, 150 from Kosovo and 135 from Romania.	1.Analyze how ethnic, national, familial and religious identity influence Roma well-being. 2.Outline areas of intervention to improve Roma well-being.	1.Roma adolescents reported lower well-being and positive affect than the rest of the adolescents in Bulgaria and Kosovo, above all. 2.The Roma identity does not correlate positively with well-being in any of the countries, even negatively in two of the countries. 3.Familial and religious identity correlate positively with well-being in all Roma groups. Regarding national identity, no significant data was found in any country, indicating the marginal role that this type of identity plays in young Roma.	1.Context conditions were not assessed. 2.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population.
Kalibatseva, Leong, Ham, Lannert & Chen, 2017	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Loss of Face questionnaire; Family Conflicts scale; CES-D; birth year, gender, class standing,	488 college students: 209 AsAs (AsA) (43%) and 279 European Americans (EA) (57%).	Explore racial differences in depression between AsA and European American by examining loss of face and	1.AsA reported higher levels of depression, loss of face, and intergenerational family conflict. 2.Loss of face and intensity of intergenerational family conflict significantly predicted depression. 3.Loss of face explained more variance in depression among AsA than among EA	1.Other culturally important variables have not been included in the analysis. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 3.Ethnic subgroups were not analyzed, and

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		family income and citizenship status.		intergenerational family conflict.	while there was no difference in intergenerational family conflict. 4.Loss of face and family conflict fully mediated the relationship between race/ethnicity and depression. Race/ethnicity indirectly affected depression through loss of face.	the results relate only to college students. 4.Qualitative measures are needed to determine associations.
Kim et al., 2017	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: household educational attainment and total household income (objective social status; OSS); MacArthur Scale of Subjective Social Status (SSS); Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory Version (child HrQOL); child race/ethnicity.	4,824 parents: 30% Blacks, 47% Latinos, and 23% Whites.	1.Analyze the relationships that parental OSS and SSS have on children’s HrQOL. 2.Explore if parental SSS mediates those relationships. 3.Determine if the associations differ by ethnicity.	1.Parental OSS was significantly related to physical HrQOL (only among Latinos) and psychosocial HrQOL (in all ethnic groups). 2.The path from parental OSS to parental SSS was consistently significant across Black, Latino, and White groups. 3.Parental SSS was not significantly associated with child physical or psychosocial HRQOL for any ethnic group.	1.Findings could not be generalized because of selection bias, exclusion from other ethnic groups. 2.Generational status in the USA was not measured.
Lim, Cappa & Patton, 2017	Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia, Serbia and Ukraine.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: questionnaire on the domestic environment and demographic variables and on	11,994 young people between 15 and 24 years old: 2,827 Roma (24%).	Analyze subjective wellbeing (life satisfaction, optimism and happiness) and its relationship with demographic factors.	There is no relationship between being Roma and life satisfaction or optimism. The Roma report being happier, although this data is not significant. Young Roma show levels of wellbeing similar to those of the general population, despite differences in living conditions.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Poor data analysis.

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		subjective wellbeing.				
Begeny and Huo, 2016	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: Likert scales on ethnic group intrastatus and identity-centrality, perceived discrimination, anxiety, and psychological distress; CES-D.	510 ethnic minority students (201 Asian/AsA and 309 Latino/Hispanic).	Assess how the processes within the intragroup status and health model function over time.	<p>1. Feeling valued among ingroup members predicts greater mental health. Feeling valued turns ethnic identity more central to self-concept, associated with more perceptions of discrimination and lower mental health.</p> <p>2. Significant associations between: intragroup status and mental health/identity-centrality; identity-centrality and discrimination; perceived discrimination and mental health.</p> <p>3. Over time: status among ethnic ingroup positively affected ethnic identity/mental health. Strength of identity-centrality negatively correlates with health and positively affected perceived discrimination, which predicts higher levels of ethnic identity and lower mental health.</p>	Data cannot truly assert causality because of observational research.
Heaslip, Hean & Parker, 2016	United Kingdom and Ireland	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	13 Roma travellers	Describe the experience of vulnerability of Roma travellers.	Six characteristics of vulnerability related to the situation of Roma travellers were found: 1) feeling defined and homogenized as a group; 2) pressured to conform to living in a certain way; 3) split in their identity; 4) loss of their cultural heritage; 5) feeling discriminated against, persecuted and threatened and 6) powerlessness, feeling that you have no voice.	<p>1. Results could not be generalizable.</p> <p>2. It was not focused on health issues.</p>

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Hu & Taylor, 2016	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: CES-D; Racial Microaggressions Scale; Ethnic Identity Scale; Racism and Life Experience Scale; Perceived Stress Scale; Buss-Durkee Hostility Inventory.	449 adults: 17.4% Whites, 30.5% AAs, 19.8% Hispanics/Latinos, 14.0% AsAs/Pacific Islanders, 3.1% Native Americans/American Indians, and 3.8% other.	1.Examine ethnic awareness in social interactions (experience of microaggressions). 2.Explore how that relationship relates to measures of mental health.	When compared to Whites, AAs endorsed being more aware of their ethnicity during social interactions, also reported having stronger ethnic identity, experiencing more racial microaggressions, and experiencing more racism. People who reported being more aware of their ethnicity during social interactions also reported more depressive symptoms, perceived stress, irritability, suspicion, and resentment.	1.Questionnaires were done online and self-reported. 2.Average age was your (32). 3.Geographical location may impact the results as some city are more diverse than others.
Jabson et al., 2016	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Medical Outcomes (wellbeing); likert scale (social support/ strain, life events, caregiving); life orientation test; Emotional Expressiveness/ Ambivalence Questionnaire; Cook-Medley Questionnaire (cynical hostility).	140,652 post-menopause women, over 60 years old: 14,616 Black or AA (9%), 6,483 Hispanic/Latino (4%) and 133,530 White (83%).	1.Identify psychosocial clusters from among health-relevant psycho-social predictors. 2.Investigate racial/ethnic differences in clusters.	1.Associations between psychosocial clusters and wellbeing were more pronounced for ethnic minority groups, especially Latino and American Indian/Alaska Native women. 2.In ethnic groups, cultural importance of social support/networks is important for disease prevention and management. 3.Hispanic and American Indian/Alaska Natives experience higher stress and trauma.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Data does not reflect a population-based sample. 3.Results may be influenced by healthy volunteer effect.
Kim & Fredriksen-Goldsen, 2016	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Lifetime	2,138 older adults who self-identified as Hispanic or non-	Test for significant differences in MHQOL between	1.Being Hispanic was significantly associated with poorer MHQOL. Poorer MHQOL among Hispanic participants is	1.Cross sectional, generalizability and

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		Discrimination Scale; SES; Social connectedness questionnaire; Perceived Stress Scale; SF-8 Health Survey (Mental Health Quality of Life-MHQOL).	Hispanic White, Lesbian, Gays and Bisexuals, including 102 Hispanic and 2,036 non-Hispanic White participants.	Hispanic and non-Hispanic White midlife and older LGB adults. 2. Test differences to investigate the explanatory factors that account for them.	explained by a higher level of perceived stress, which is associated with lower SES, higher frequency of lifetime discrimination, and lack of social connectedness. 2. Hispanic LGB midlife and older adults face heightened likelihood of sexual identity-related lifetime discrimination, which is linked to higher levels of perceived stress and lower levels of MHQOL.	causal inferences are restricted. 2. Questionnaires only available in English. 3. Hispanic sample was disproportionately smaller.
Liang & Molenaar, 2016	United States	A cross-sectional mixed study: General Ethnic Discrimination Scale; Own-Group Conformity Pressure Scale; Unjust Views Scale; Anger Rumination Scale; Negative Affect Scale.	215 adults: 129 Hispanic/ Latino/a, 24 AA/Black, 17 multiracial, 6 Asian/AsA, 4 American Indian/ Alaska Native, 4 Arab American/ Persian and 4 Pacific Islander.	Examine the mediating role of Beliefs in an unjust World (BUW) in the association between two ethnicity-related stressors (ERS) and two outcomes—negative affect and anger rumination.	1. The more individuals encounter ERS, both own-group conformity pressures and perceived ethnic discrimination (PED), the more likely they are to endorse unjust world beliefs. 2. These cognitive schemas, in turn, are positively and significantly associated with anger rumination and negative affect. 3. BUW mediated both the association between PED and negative mood as well as PED and anger rumination, provide additional support for earlier contentions that BUW is an outcome of significant stressors and a predictor of psychological functioning.	1. Correlational design: cannot determine the direction of the associations/statements of causality. 2. Sample was recruited from a university and comprised mainly of women and may not be generalized.
Marshall-Fabien & Miller, 2016	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: CES-D; Every Day Discrimination Scale; Likert scales (social support and	1,108 elders (aged 55 years and older): 837 AAs (AA) and 271 CBs (CB).	1. Examine demographic factors, stress, social networks, and depressive symptoms. 2. Determine if ethnicity	1. Significant associations between SES/ education/income and depressive symptoms among AA; same trend among CB but not statistically significant. Significant associations between material hardship/ discrimination and depressive symptoms among AA. Social support was associated with depressive symptoms	1. Discrepancy in the relative sample sizes of AA and CB. Also, ethnic subgroups have not been considered. 2. Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.

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AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
		connectedness); age, gender, ethnicity, marital status, education, annual household income, material hardship.		moderates the relationship between psychological distress and depressive symptoms.	among CB. Social connectedness was associated with depressive symptoms for both groups. 4.Models determined that SES, education, material hardship and discrimination were significantly associated with depressive symptoms for AA and CB.	3.Social support and connectedness measures could have not been sensitive.
Na & Hample, 2016	Canada	Cross sectional, quantitative study: Likert scale (social integration, homophily, global self-rated health, life satisfaction, happiness, personal control, sense of belonging, generalized trust); education and income.	11,548 individuals: 8,617 native-born Whites, 324 Aboriginal, 221 native-born visible minority immigrants and 1,363 White immigrants.	Explore how sense of belonging, personal control, and generalized trust mediate the pathways from social integration to self-reported health outcomes.	1.Aboriginal Canadians had larger networks of other friends, greater numbers of other friends in close proximity, and more active contacts with their friends in comparison to Whites. Native-born whites, visible minorities and Aboriginals had similar levels of volunteering and religious attendance. All groups were less likely to be homophilous in ethnicity and language than White Canadians. 2.All three-native born groups felt the same level of personal control. Non- Whites reported a significantly lower sense of belonging and generalized trust. Aboriginals reported a significantly lower level of physical and mental health, education levels and household income than native-born Whites. All reported significantly lower levels of life satisfaction compared to the native-born majority. 3.Psychological mediators partially mediated the relationship between SES and health. Negative effects of aboriginal, native-born visible minority or immigrant visible minority status on health were	1.Data analysis reflect associations among variables, not causality. 2.Language barrier conducting the survey. 3.White immigrants and visible minority immigrants treated as a homogeneous group.

Table 4. Data chart of the main obtained results on other racialized groups.

AUTHORS, YEAR	COUNTRY	METHOD	SAMPLE	OBJECTIVES	MAIN RESULTS	LIMITATIONS
					either partially or completely mediated psychologically.	
Pereira et al., 2016	Portugal	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI); time of unemployment.	71 unemployed adults (31 Roma).	Analyze the differences in mental health between unemployed Roma and non-Roma.	1.Non-Roma obtained significantly higher scores than Roma in different areas: obsession-compulsion, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, anxiety, paranoid ideation, psychoticism, and in global severity. 2.Unemployment conditions have a much more negative impact on the mental health of non-Roma participants.	1.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis. 2.Results could not be generalizable.
Stronge, Sengupta, Barlow, Osborne, Houkamau & Sibley, 2016	New Zealand	Mixed quantitative study: Identity centrality scale (ethnic identity); Satisfaction with Life Scale; NZ Deprivation Index; questions on perceived discrimination and support for Maori rights.	Cross-sectional phase: 1,981 Maori participants. Longitudinal phase: 1,373 Maori participants.	Analyze associations between wellbeing and engagement in collective action with the recognition of discrimination and ingroup identity.	1.Perceived discrimination was positively related to ethnic identity and support for Maori rights, and negatively related with life satisfaction. Ethnic identity was positively associated with life satisfaction and support for Maori rights. 2.Perceived discrimination had a positive indirect effect on support for Maori rights via ethnic identity. 3.1 year later, perceived discrimination was positively associated with ethnic identity (and in reverse it was the same) and negatively associated with life satisfaction. Ethnic identification was positively associated with levels of life satisfaction. 4.Satisfaction with life was unassociated with political mobilization. Perceived discrimination was positively associated with support for political rights 1 year later.	1.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis. 2.Measures used could not be sensitive enough.

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					5.The indirect pathway between perceived discrimination and support for political rights via ethnic identity was significant.	
Zvolensky, Jardin, Garey, Robles & Sharp, 2016	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Social, Attitudinal, Familial and Environmental scale (acculturative stress); Multidimensional experiential avoidance questionnaire; Inventory of Depression and Anxiety Symptoms; Positive and negative affect schedule; Financial strain questionnaire.	1,095 minority college students: 15.1% AA, 45.3% Hispanic, 32.5% Asian, and 7.1% other races/ethnicities.	Examine the interactive effects of acculturative stress and experiential avoidance in relation to anxiety and depressive symptoms.	1.Acculturative stress was related to greater levels of suicidal symptoms, social anxiety, and anxious arousal among minority college students with higher levels of experiential avoidance; no significant interaction for depressive symptoms. Both main effects were significantly related to depression. 2.Acculturative stress and experiential avoidance each independently explained unique variance in each of dependent measures. The only exception to this pattern of results was suicidal symptoms wherein only acculturative stress showcased a significant effect. Additionally, acculturative stress and experiential avoidance shared only 13% of variance with one another, suggesting they represent related, but distinct constructs.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inference. 2.Sample largely female. 3.Could be applicable to other more culturally specific manifestations of distress or stress.
Brittian et al., 2015	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Scale of Ethnic Experience (perceived ethnic group discrimination); Ethnic Identity Scale	2,315 college students (63% Latino, 37% Black)	1.Study the associations between perceptions of ethnic group discrimination and depressive symptoms.	1.Black students reported higher levels of discrimination and ethnic identity exploration. Latinos reported higher levels of ethnic identity affirmation Women reported higher levels of discrimination, exploration, resolution and affirmation. 2.Discrimination was positively related to exploration and depressive symptoms. Identity resolution and affirmation	1.Overrepresentation of women. 2.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 3.Possible confusion between race and ethnicity; possible stereotype threat.

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		(exploration, resolution and affirmation); CES-D.		2.Explore the mediator role of dimensions of ethnic identity (exploration, resolution and affirmation).	correlated negatively with depressive symptoms. Exploration correlated positively with resolution, which also correlated positively with affirmation. Discrimination was negatively related to affirmation for Latino students. 3.Discrimination was indirectly associated with depressive symptoms through identity affirmation among Latinos. Resolution was indirectly associated with depressive symptoms through affirmation among Blacks and Latinos.	
Garbarski, 2015	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: Likert scales (early life and persistent health risk factors); CES-D; RSES; locus of control; SES.	12,686 people from three racial and ethnic groups: non-black non-Hispanics (Whites), black non-Hispanics and Hispanics or Latinos.	Examine how disadvantage factors (early life and persistent exposure to health risk factors, status-resource interactions) are associated to depressive symptoms at midlife.	1.Compared to whites, Hispanic women's depressive symptoms are related to persistent health limitations, poverty status and educational attainment while Black women's depressive symptoms are related to persistent health limitations. 2.The positive association between depressive symptoms and persistent health limitations is larger for black women compared to white women. 3.If Hispanic and black men took on the total associational characteristics of white men, this would increase depressive symptoms for Hispanic/Latino and black men and thus increase the observed disparities.	1.The causal ordering of relationships cannot be parsed. 2.It does not examine the total effect of early life and persistent health risk factors.
Hughes, Kiecolt, Keith, & Demo, 2015	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: RSES; Pearlin's Mastery scale; CES-D.	3,570 respondents.	AA Understand how group identification and ingroup evaluation affect self-attitudes and	The more closely AAs identified with their group, the more positively they evaluated it. Racial group identification was associated with higher self-esteem and mastery and lower depressive symptoms. Positive ingroup evaluation also was	1.Data are cross-sectional, being impossible to determine whether identity dimensions

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				psychological wellbeing among AAs.	related to more positive self-attitudes and lower depressive symptoms. Higher internalized racism impacted racial identification with other AAs with lower mastery and higher depressive symptoms.	influence well-being or the reverse. 2.Data set did not contain outgroup evaluations.
Kamberi, Martinovic & Verkuyten, 2015	Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia and Macedonia.	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Likert scales (subjective well-being, income, health, education, quality of housing, discrimination, ethnic identification).	11,997 participants: 8,399 Roma (70%), from twelve european countries.	Examine whether the Roma population has lower levels of subjective well-being than the rest of the population.	1.Roma have lower levels of health, a lower level of education, half of the income than non-Roma and perceive greater discrimination (the trend is the same in all countries although the strength of the associations differs). 2.Significantly, the Roma show a lower level of happiness and life satisfaction in the twelve countries.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Results are not generalizable to other countries. 3.Sample could not represent the whole Roma population.
McNeil Smith & Taylor, 2015	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: frequency scale (alcohol, marijuana use); checklists (social stress); Everyday Discrimination Scale.	426 young people: 201 black non-Hispanic and 225 white non-Hispanic males.	Examine the association of different types of stressors on substance use among black and white teenage boys.	1.High exposure to a wide range of risk factors does not translate into proportional rates of quantity and frequency of substance use. 2.Exposure to stress was associated with substance use among black youth, and that this pattern of findings explained greater variation in alcohol and marijuana use compared to white youth.	1.Sample may not be generalizable. 2.Relatively small sample size and cross-sectional design may undermine data analysis.
Pappa et al., 2015	Greece	Cross-sectional quantitative study: SF-36 Health Survey.	1,068 Roma adults living in settlements.	1.Evaluate the HrQOL of the Roma. 2.Analyze the factors that	1.Roma men, the youngest and those with a partner report significantly higher scores on all scales compared to women, the elderly and the single people.	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.

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				determine the HrQOL of the Roma.	2.On the ‘vitality’ and ‘mental health’ scales, illiterate people have a lower level of health; high family income is associated with a higher level of health. 3.Having a stable home for the last 3 years increases the perception of health. Access to basic material resources (electricity, indoor drainage, and drinkable water) are associated with higher scores on most scales.	2.Results could not be generalizable to all the Roma groups.
Rogers, 2015	United Kingdom	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews, focus group and narrative conversations (2 discussion groups and 1 music, tales workshop) followed by nine individual narrative conversations.	8 English Travellers and 8 England Roma. All females between the ages of fifteen and mid-fifties.	1.Present emerging findings from on-going research studies exploring the bereavement experiences of Roma and Traveller families. 2.Considers resilience in relation to the bereavement experiences.	1.Close relationships between individuals promotes resilience and can provide barriers to exacerbated health risk. 2.A lack of intergenerational resilience and learnt responses to grief and bereavement are likely to result in the high levels of grief- related mental health problems. 3.The strong family attachments that should provide the balance in their lives, and which in many ways help them to develop resilience to the hardships of life are important in supporting them through physical and practical struggles, resilience in the face of bereavement (something which is difficult for anyone to cope with) appears to be compromised by the overriding cultural need to protect family members by asserting stoicism.	None mentioned.
Shadick, Dagirmanjian & Barbot, 2015	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: CORE Survey (suicide risk); Patient Health	4,345 students: 79.9% heterosexual; 50% white, 11.9% Asian/Pacific Islander, 0.7%	Collect information on differential suicide rates among first-year university students based on	1.There is a complex relationship between minority status and the risk of suicide. 2.Students of color, as a group, are slightly less likely than their white peers to support a high risk of suicide.	1.LGB students and students of colour were placed in these categories based on the theoretical implications of their

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		Questionnaire 9; Beck Depression Inventory II.	American/Alaska Native, 7% "other".	membership of one or more marginalized groups.	3.The finding is consistent with general population statistics that young white adults have higher suicide rates than their black peers.	status as minors. 2.Methodological limitations.
Dimitrova et al., 2014	Bulgaria	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Bulgarian Mainstream Identity Scale, Roma Ethnic Identity Scale, Family Identity Scale, Religious Identity Scale and Satisfaction with Life Scale.	194 Roma adolescents (13 to 20 years old) and their mothers.	Investigate the relationship between ethnic, familial and religious identity and psychological well-being.	1.Familial identity is stronger compared to Roma, Bulgarian and religious identity for both adolescents and their mothers. 2.The four areas of identity are positively related to collective identity, which in turn is positively related to the wellbeing of adolescents and their mothers. The collective identity of mothers predicts the wellbeing of adolescents. 3.Roma identity and wellbeing are not related. The Bulgarian identity is indirectly related to well-being and happiness.	1.Results are not generalizable to other countries. 2.Only mothers were included. 3.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Hill, Cook & Whitfield, 2014	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: education; questions on sense of control; Kessler and colleagues' 6-items (psychological distress).	1,504 community dwelling adults: whites, blacks and Mexican Americans.	1.Examine if education promotes skills and abilities equally across ethnic groups. 2.Explore education-control-distress (E-C-D) model validity across ethnic groups.	1.Higher education is related to higher sense of control across race and ethnic groups. 2.Respondents who report greater control also tend to report fewer symptoms of psychological distress. The analyses suggest that the E-C-D model is valid across race and ethnic groups.	1.Ethnic and racial groups were underrepresented. 2.Measure of education is based on a coarse ordinal measurement Scale, being less reliable.
Marquine et al., 2014	United States	A cross-sectional study	252 adults: 126 Hispanics and 126 non-Hispanic whites aged 50 and older.	1.Examine differences in life satisfaction between older	1. English-speaking Hispanics aged 50 and older seemed to be more satisfied with their lives than their non-Hispanic white counterparts, and these differences were	1.Only English-speaking Hispanics were included, and their level of education was higher than the

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				Hispanic and non-Hispanic white. 2. Identify specific factors associated with differences.	mainly due to a greater spirituality among Hispanics. 2. Multivariate analyses testing the influence of these three factors (spiritual experiences, religious practices, and compassion) on the association between ethnicity and life satisfaction showed that greater spirituality among Hispanics explained the ethnic differences in life satisfaction.	general U.S. Hispanic population. 2. Limited information on factors that may be relevant to Hispanics.
Nystad, Spein & Ingstad, 2014	Norway	Cross-sectional qualitative study: activities related to reindeer herding, recreation and use of natural resources.	22 youth aged 13 to 19; 15 were younger adolescents, and seven were older adolescents. All were self-identified as Sami.	1. Provide a description of how some factors function in the lives of Sami. 2. Investigate how adolescents navigate and negotiate community resilience resources on their way to adulthood.	1. For Sami youth, cultural continuity seems to play a significant role in building and maintaining social networks. These networks are maintained by kinship and extended family and extended godparent traditions (traditional wedding ceremonies, yoik, naming traditions). 2. Youth with reindeer herding affiliation seem to be more enculturated in traditional practices than do other Sami youth. 3. Same networks that provided social support might also cause stress for adolescents if they feel they are excluded/demanded to conform. 4. The expectation to care and show responsibility to others through these networks can also be associated with pressure when the value of the group assumes more importance than the individual.	1. Self-selection of participants and small sample size limits the generalizability. 2. Interviews were conducted in Sami and Norwegian and some of the meaning may have been distorted.
Omma & Petersen, 2014	Sweden	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Kidscreen	121 Sami schoolchildren	1. Examine differences in HrQOL of	1. 50% of Sami reported negative treatment; 25% reported being unfairly treated by teachers; 15%	1. 30% nonparticipation rate and high dropout of Sami children.

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		questionnaire (HrQOL); additional questions on negative treatment because of Sami ethnicity and enculturation.		Sami schoolchildren and the general child HrQOL. 2.Explore experienced ethnic-related negative treatment and its association with HrQOL.	experienced teachers saying negative things about the Sami. These experiences were associated with lower functioning and wellbeing. 2.74% reported high social acceptance; 60% reported low functioning and wellbeing in the school. 3. Sami reported lower functioning and wellbeing in school and with regard to financial resources, and lower levels of social support and relations with parents. Negligible differences were found in psychological wellbeing, but in higher grades Sami psychological wellbeing decreased.	2.Using norm data from Swedish population does not allow for adjustments; specific characteristics of the data.
Postmus, McMahon, Silva-Martínez & Warrenner, 2014	United States	Cross-sectional qualitative study: semi-structured interviews with IPV Latinas survivors.	25 Latina IPV survivors. Almost half of the community identify as Hispanic, with the majority of Mexican and Puerto Rican backgrounds.	Explore the help-seeking challenges faced by a community sample of 25 Latina intimate partner violence (IPV) survivors.	1.Information is provided about help-seeking barriers and supportive factors encountered by Latina survivors of IPV in one setting. 2.The findings are specific to one particular community, they suggest important next steps for better understanding on how to address IPV among the Latina population. 3.The findings support the ecological model as a useful framework for organizing our understanding of help seeking, as the women reported obstacles and support systems occurring at various levels of interactions.	1.The study uses a purpose-full sampling technique; hence, it is not random and limited in applicability to other Latina populations. 2.Small sample size and not necessarily representative of the broader community.
Alex & Lehti, 2013	Sweden	Cross-sectional qualitative study.	9 Sami women and 4 Roma women.	Analyze experiences of well-being and	1.Factors that contribute to well-being: belonging to a healthy family, spirituality, cultural norms related to health promotion	1. Small sample size of Roma women.

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				discomfort among Sami and Roma women in Sweden.	(daily contact with friends and family and living collectively) and having lived a life of their own. 2.Factors that contribute to discomfort: living subordinate to the majority society (those who see the Roma as inferior and without education), living in a hierarchical family (women subordinate to men) and living with tuberculosis.	2.The variable 'age' was not exhaustively controlled.
Assari, 2013	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Likert scales (church attendance, church-based support, self-rated health and life satisfaction).	AAs (n = 3570), CBs (n = 1621), and Whites (n = 891).	Test if social support and ethnicity mediate/moderate the association between religion involvement and subjective health.	1.Frequency of church attendance had a significant and positive association with mental health and life satisfaction among all ethnic groups. 2.Frequency of church attendance was also correlated with positive and negative social support among all ethnic groups. 3.Church-based social support fully mediated the association between frequency of church attendance and overall life satisfaction among AAs but not among CBs, or Whites.	Did not include measures of stress.
Davis & Wu, 2013	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Telephone health survey-BRFSS (basic demographic variables, health risk behaviors, preventive health practices, health care access, and	1,1 million respondents between 25-65 years old: 8% AAs, 7% Hispanics, 2% Asians. 80% Non-Hispanics Whites. Native Americans were excluded.	1.Investigate differences in group-specific income effects. 2.Distinguish empirically between information and solidarity effects. 3.Use data on subjective wellbeing to	1.Individual's racial and ethnic identity matters in determining the reference group with which he or she engages in social comparisons. For Whites, life satisfaction is decreasing in average group income; among Blacks, life satisfaction increases in average group income. No significant relationship between group income and happiness was found for Hispanics or Asians. 2.Decomposing the comparison income effect into three parts (negative status effect and positive information and	None mentioned

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		subjective well-being.).		identify and test theories of Black solidarity.	solidarity effects): strong support for the existence of Black solidarity, but no support for the existence of empirically significant information effects for Blacks. 3. Feelings of social solidarity decrease with a group's share of state population-consistent with the social salience theory of solidarity. Solidarity effects play a role in social comparisons for both Blacks and Whites, though they are strongest for Blacks.	
Dimitrova, 2013	Bulgaria	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Sociodemographic questionnaire; Bulgarian Mainstream Identity Scale; Familial Identity Scale, Religious Identity Scale; Satisfaction with Life Scale; Positive Affective Schedule.	606 participants with Roma (n= 207) and Bulgarian (n= 399) background. Age varied from 11 to 18 years.	Investigate links among domains of important for psychological wellbeing, during early and middle adolescence in Roma minority and Bulgarian majority groups.	1. Collective identity: Bulgarian adolescents show lower levels of religious identification than their Roma peers. No significant differences among the groups for Bulgarian and familial identity. 2. Collective identity x wellbeing: Roma youth scoring significantly lower on satisfaction with life. No significant differences between Roma and Bulgarian groups were found for positive affect. 3. Collective identity has the same relationship with wellbeing in the two ethnic groups; Bulgarian, familial, and religious identity were positively and significantly related to wellbeing, irrespective of ethnic group membership.	1. Impact of discrimination and segregation assessed indirectly. 2. Longitudinal design would be more appropriate. 3. Lack of other important demographic information, specifically for the Roma group. 4. Self-report measures.
Jang, Park, Kang & Chiriboga, 2013	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: self-rated mental health; CES-D;	Population-based study of non-institutionalized older adults aged 57 to 85; 2,110 non-Hispanic Whites, 509	1. Explore ethnic differences in self-rated mental health. 2. Explore within-group variations in	The CES-D scores of the minority groups were consistently higher than that of non-Hispanic Whites. Significance was obtained in the interactions between depressive symptoms and age in Blacks and between depressive symptoms and	1. Using cross-sectional data difficults causal inferences. 2. Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias.

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		demographic variables.	Blacks and 304 Hispanics.	the impact of depressive symptoms on self-rated mental health.	chronic conditions in Hispanics, and further analyses revealed that the predictability of depressive symptoms to self-rated mental health was substantially weakened among Blacks of advanced ages and Hispanics with multiple chronic conditions.	
McGorrian, Hamid, Fitzpatrick, Daly, Malone & Kelleher, 2013	Ireland	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (HrQOL); likert scale (self-rated health, social support); experience of discrimination scale.	8,492 families.	Examine the associations between sociodemographic and lifestyle factors with poor mental health in Irish Travellers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Travellers experience discrimination and bereavement, which negatively influence their mental health. 2. The importance of contextualising mental health symptomatology and using systematic methods of measurement. 3. Clear implications for policy and may be relevant to other indigenous ethnic groups worldwide, that face similar circumstances. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Using self-reported measures, without clinical or cultural validation, may be a cause of bias. 2.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Syed et al., 2013	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study. Multigroup Ethnic Identity; Ethnic Identity; Erikson Psychosocial Inventory Scale; RSES; Questionnaire for Eudaimonic Wellbeing; Scales of Psychosocial Wellbeing;	3,637 participants between the ages of 18 and 30 years: 39% Latino, 26% East Asian, 23% Black, 8% South Asian, and 4% Middle Eastern.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Explore how ethnic identity exploration (participation and search) is associated with wellbeing. 2.Explore how identity coherence/confusion mediate these relationships. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Participation was positively associated with wellbeing, search was negatively associated with wellbeing. Ethnic identity participation was positively linked with general identity coherence and negatively with confusion. Ethnic identity search was positively associated with general identity confusion. 2.Identity coherence and identity confusion were both strongly associated with wellbeing. Ethnic identity participation was indirectly associated with well-being through both general identity coherence and general identity confusion. Ethnic identity search was 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Models tested were all cross-sectional, limiting ability to make causal ordering. 2.The two exploration measures used different response scales. 3. ¾ female college students sample might not be generalizable.

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		Satisfaction with Life Scale.			negatively linked with well-being through identity confusion but not through identity coherence.	
Thoma & Huebner, 2013	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Schedule of Racist Events; questions on antigay discrimination; National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health (substance use); CES-D.	156 AA and 120 AA mixed: 59% identified as gay or lesbian, 27% as bisexual, and 14% identified as “queer” or with some other sexual orientation.	Describe how racist and antigay discrimination combine to predict substance use, depressive symptoms and suicidal ideation in a sample of AA LGB adolescents.	1.Higher levels of antigay/racist discrimination were independently associated with greater depressive symptoms and suicidal ideation. 2.Antigay/racist discrimination predicted a significant variance in depressive symptoms, although racist discrimination was stronger predictor. 4.Antigay discrimination, but not racist, was associated with suicidal ideation. 5.Racist discrimination was associated with marijuana use. Neither form of discrimination was associated with alcohol use, or smoking.	1.Cross sectional design. 2.Dissimilar measures of mistreatment (racist multiple contexts, antigay school setting). 3.Only examined suicidal ideation.
Tobler et al., 2013	United States	Cross sectional quantitative study: frequency and intensity of perceived discrimination, alcohol and marijuana use, physical aggression, delinquency, victimization, depression, suicidal ideation, sexual behavior.	2,490 adolescents: 51% AA, 31,4% Hispanic, 17,8% White.	Examine perceived frequency and intensity of racial/ethnic discrimination and its associations with high-risk behaviors/ conditions.	1.Most adolescents (73%) experienced racial/ethnic discrimination. 42% of experiences were “somewhat-” or “very disturbing.” 2.Adolescents who experienced discrimination were more likely to report greater physical aggression, delinquency, suicidal ideation, younger age at first oral sex, unprotected sex and more lifetime sexual partners. 3.Experiences of discrimination contribute to maladaptive behavioral and mental health outcomes among adolescents. Strong associations were found between perceived discrimination and negative mental health outcomes, including	1. Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Not generalizable to larger variations to culture and context.

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					depression and suicidal ideation. These associations did not vary by race/ethnicity.	
Gray & Montgomery, 2012	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Childhood Trauma Questionnaire; Trauma Symptom Checklist; Drug Use screening inventory; Composite international diagnostic interview (CIDI); perceived discrimination and Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure.	168 Black and Hispanic adolescent girls.	Examine the links between maltreatment, posttraumatic stress symptoms, ethnicity-specific factors (i.e., perceived discrimination, ethnic identity, ethnic orientation), and alcohol and/or other drug (AOD) problems.	1.Perceived discrimination significantly moderated the relation between maltreatment and posttraumatic stress symptoms. 2.Discrimination double traumatized youth by distorting their perceptions of themselves and compounding their pre-existing negative feelings. Perceived discrimination is a chronic stressor, salient for many ethnic minorities. 3.Low levels of ethnic orientation were associated with an increased negative impact of maltreatment on AOD problems as compared to mean and high ethnic orientation levels. Ethnic orientation acted as a protective mechanism in this relation.	Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Hansen & Sørli, 2012	Norway	Cross-sectional quantitative study: ethnicity, Hopkins Symptoms Check List; likert scales (ethnic discrimination and bullying, SES)	13,703 individuals who responded adequately to questions about mental health: 34.6% Sami, 7.9% Kven, and 57.5% Ethnic Norwegian.	1.Determine the prevalence of psychological distress within Sami and non-Sami 2.Investigate the associations between ethnic discrimination and psychological distress.	Ethnic discrimination was associated with increased levels of psychological distress. In total, 6.5% of men and 10% of women reported experiencing psychological distress in the clinical range (measured by HSCL>1.85). Psychological distress in men was more prevalent in Sami and in Kvens. Both male and female Sami respondents reported being more discriminated against than Ethnic Norwegians. Females sought psychological treatment more frequently	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 3.Measures of psychological distress developed in Western society.

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					than males. Education proved to be a protection factor on female participants.	
Hassler & Eklund, 2012	Sweden	Cross-sectional quantitative study: short-form Health Survey (physical and mental component) and the Antonovsky's Sense of Coherence Scale.	99 Roma adults	Investigate the relationship between the sense of coherence and self-reported health.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Roma show lower scores in both physical and mental health, being these significantly different than the non-Roma Swedish population. 2. The sense of coherence was significantly lower in the Roma population; furthermore, it correlates significantly with mental and physical health. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Questionnaires based on a western way of life being not sufficiently valid for Roma. 2. Access difficulties to these populations.
Janevic, Jankovic & Bradley, 2012	Serbia	Cross-sectional quantitative study.	14,313 participants, 267 Roma (1,9%).	Analyze differences in self-perceived health between Roma and non-Roma.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Significant differences between Roma and non-Roma: the Roma reported lower educational level, higher poverty level and higher unemployment rate. 2. Roma are more than twice as likely to report worse health than non-Roma. 3. Roma women are at higher risk of experiencing poor health. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The meaning of health may be different for each group. 2. The results cannot be generalized to other populations. 3. Underestimation of the Roma sample.
Kelley & Lowe, 2012	United States	Cross-sectional qualitative study: story theory-guided approach.	Written stories of stress were gathered from 50 Cherokee-Keetoowah Native Americans adolescents ranging in ages from 14 to 18 years.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe the health challenge of stress. 2. Identify approaches used to manage stress. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On health challenge of stress themes were: burden of expectation (self-expectations and the expectations of others), imposing feelings/actions of others and relationship disruption with family or friends. 2. On stress management, adolescents highlighted: connecting with valued others, engaging in meaningful activities, and choosing a positive attitude about change. 	None mentioned

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Lee & Turney, 2012	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: CES-D; Revised UCLA Loneliness Scale.	3,102 adults stratified into 343 neighborhood clusters.	Explore how chronic everyday and major lifetime discrimination are linked to mental health and its association by race/ethnicity, gender and SES.	<p>1.Blacks report more everyday and major discrimination than whites. Hispanics report more major discrimination, but not more everyday discrimination, than whites. Men report more everyday and major discrimination than women.</p> <p>2.Higher values on everyday discrimination increases loneliness and hostility. Occurrence and frequency of major discrimination is associated with mental health impairments. Women report more depressive symptoms and less hostility than men. Blacks and Hispanics report less loneliness and more hostility.</p> <p>3.Education is negatively correlated with depressive symptoms and hostility. Major life events are associated with more depressive symptoms. Perceived social support is inversely related to mental health impairments.</p>	1.Major discrimination scale measures lifetime events, while recent experiences could be more strongly associated with mental health.
Lincoln, Taylor, Chatters & Joe, 2012	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: World Mental Health Composite International Diagnostic Interview (suicide behaviors); Likert scales (familial emotional support, negative interaction).	3,570 AA (68%), and 1,621 blacks of Caribbean descent (31%).	Analyze the relationships between perceived emotional support, familial negative interactions and suicide behaviors.	<p>1.Emotional support is significantly associated with lower odds of suicide attempts and ideation, whereas negative interaction with family is significantly associated with higher suicide behaviors.</p> <p>2.The relationship between emotional support and negative interactions with suicide attempts was greater for CBs: emotional support decreased their risk of suicide attempts by 50 % more while experiencing negative interactions with family members duplicated the risk for suicide attempts compared to AAs.</p>	<p>1.Results are not generalizable to other ethnic subgroups; people who were not English-speakers were excluded.</p> <p>2.Using self-reported measures may cause underreporting.</p> <p>3.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.</p>

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Mathew, Gayman, Cislo, Goidel & Ueno, 2012	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: CES-D; Provisions of Social Relations scale; RSES; chronic stress; SES.	1,411 young adults (ages 18–23).	Assess SES and race-ethnic group differences in the stress-buffering effects of perceived social support and self-esteem.	Stress-buffering effects of social support self-esteem do not vary by SES. Independent of SES and other study controls, non-Hispanic whites experience greater stress-buffering effects from social support than AAs and AAs experience greater stress-buffering effects from self-esteem than Cubans and Nicaraguan.	1.Sample may not be generalizable. 2.Cross-sectional nature, complicates causal inferences. 3.Other variables may have been relevant.
Oates & Goode, 2012	United States	Longitudinal questionnaire study: CES-D; latent religiosity (public, private, subjective); Pearlin Mastery Scale; Stress exposure (chronic financial stress, illnesses, negative life events); socio demographics.	874 black and 1,906 white participants in both the first (1986) and second (1989) waves of longitudinal face-to-face surveys.	Investigate variation among black and white Americans in the impact of religiosity and mastery on psychological distress.	1.Religiosity suppress stress exposure and enhance access to coping resources and positive social support. In blacks, public and private religiosity effects are significantly higher and benefits forestalling of financial stress; public religiosity benefits mental health, positive social support and enhances mastery. In whites, religiosity significantly inhibitive negative interactions with friends and relatives; negative public religiosity affects undesirable life events; subjective religiosity elevates financial stress. Private Religiosity x Undesirable Life Events interaction among blacks is significantly higher. 2.Mastery significantly suppresses subsequent distress levels (effect is bigger among whites), inhibits stress exposure (also financial stress) and boosts access to social support (bigger among whites). Mastery appears to forestall financial stress among blacks especially. 3.Effects of stressor constructs at wave 1 on religiosity dimensions, mastery, coping resources and social support at wave 2 are generally no more pronounced than effects	1.Mastery and religiosity measures may not have considered exposure to financial stress or access to social support. 2.Ignores possible causal relationships among sociodemographic control measures.

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					of religiosity constructs and mastery at wave 1 on stressors at wave 2.	
Omma, Jacobsson & Patersen, 2012	Sweden	Cross-sectional population-based quantitative study: likert scales (health, perceived stress, social relationship, experience of negative treatment, enculturation, socio-demographics).	876 persons aged 18-28 and involved in Sami associated activities.	1. Investigate the health of Sami. 2. Explore the relationship between health and experience of negative societal treatment due to ethnicity and socio-demographic background factors.	1. Most of the young Sami reported feeling healthy, but close to half of the group reported often having worries, often forgetting things and often experiencing lack of time for doing needed things 2. Women and those living alone reported a more negative health. 3. Half of the group had perceived bad treatment because of Sami ethnicity, and this was negatively associated with some aspects of mental health.	1. Response rate was 59% due to problems reaching youth. 2. More men in the dropout group (43% vs. 68%). 3. Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.
Wallander et al., 2012	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: PedsQL (Pediatrics Quality of Life).	4,824 youths: 30% AA, 47% Hispanic, and 23% white.	1. Examine racial/ethnic disparities in HrQOL, and overall health status among AA, Hispanic, and white. 2. Explore if SES and family contextual variables mediate any disparities.	Marked racial/ethnic disparities were observed across all measures of HRQOL and health status, favoring white children and especially disfavoring Hispanic children. Most of these disparities were no longer significant after adjusting for SES and other family contextual differences that were observed among these racial/ethnic groups. Only disparities in parent-reported overall health status and self-reported global self-worth remained.	1. Observational design prevents from examining causes of disparities. 2. Not generalizable.
Williams et al., 2012	United States and South Africa (SA)	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Pearlin's mastery scale; RSES;	In United States: 3,570 AAs, 1,621 blacks of Caribbean descent and 891 non-Hispanic whites.	1. Identify levels and characteristics of discrimination that affect psychological functioning.	1. USA: AA and CB have higher self-esteem and racial identity; AA have lower income and education. Inverse association between everyday discrimination/stress and mastery/ self-esteem. Positive relation between education/income and mastery	1. Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2. Equivalence of constructs across language or cultural

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		acute and everyday racial/non-racial discrimination; stress and global life events; ethnicity, SES, education, income.	In South Africa: 4,351 adults (Blacks, Coloured, Indian and Whites).	2.Analyze how perceptions of bias and risk factors affect self-esteem and mastery.	and between racial identification and self-esteem. Controlling stressors, AA score higher on mastery than whites. Higher negative effect of discrimination at lower income and education. 2.SA: non-whites report lower levels of mastery, self-esteem, income, education and employment. Discrimination and life events are inversely related to mastery and self-esteem even after controlling stress. Racial identity, material resources and education are positively related to mastery and self-esteem.	subgroups was not measured. 3.Limited assessment of some factors.
Ayalon & Gum, 2011	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Self-report Psychosocial Questionnaire.	6,455 Whites, 716 Latinos and 1,214 Blacks.	Evaluate the relationships between perceived exposure to major lifetime discrimination, everyday discrimination and mental health.	1.30% of the general population reported at least one type of major lifetime discrimination almost 45% of Black older adults reported such discrimination. 2., Latinos were significantly less likely to report any everyday discrimination (64.2%), whereas Blacks reported the greatest frequency of everyday discrimination. 3. Whites reported the highest levels of life satisfaction and the lowest levels of depressive symptoms. 4.The relationships between discrimination and mental health outcomes were stronger for White compared to Black older adults, 5.Everyday discrimination was still significantly associated with outcomes for Black older adults.	1.Does not allow for inferences about direction of influence. 2.Cultural and social resources beneficial for ethnic minorities were not taken into account. 3. The subjective nature of discrimination is not taken into consideration.

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Bals, Turi, Viterrso, Skre & Kvernmo, 2011	Norway	A cross-sectional quantitative study: Hopkins Symptoms Checklist-1; Likert scales (spend time in wilderness, friend approval, family connectedness, conflict with parents).	4,449 adolescents: 450 (10%) were indigenous Sami and 3,999 (90%) were non-Sami.	Explore the relationship between symptoms of anxiety and depression and family factors in indigenous Sami and non-Sami boys and girls.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Family income was to a lesser degree related to internalization symptoms for Sami youth than non-Sami youth. 2. For all groups except for Sami girls, family conflict and moving was associated with increasing symptoms. 3. Sami boys differed from the other three groups with regard to the relationship between family connectedness and symptom level. 4. The relationship between internalization symptoms and family income, moving frequency, family connectedness, and conflict with parents showed strong interaction effects between gender and ethnicity. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cross-sectional design: cannot come to any definitive conclusions. 2. Small effect size.
Fothergill, Ensminger, Robertson, Green, Thorpe, & Juon, 2011	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: Likert scales; Physical functioning scale of the SF-36; self-rated health; - anxious mood-depressed mood (Health outcomes); reports of regular church attendance/ participation in any secular organization (Community	556 AA mothers	Assess the effects of Community Engagement on both physical and mental health among an older population of AA women.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Women engaged only later in life in either religious or secular organizations reported better physical and mental health at that time than those who were never involved. 2. Early only CE did not have a significant impact on later health compared no CE. 3. Women with persistent CE were significantly more likely to report better self-rated health, less frequent anxious mood, and less frequent depressed mood. Persistently engaged women were significantly less likely than those engaged only early on to report more frequent anxious mood and depressed mood. Persistent CE did not have a stronger influence on health than did later only engagement. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generalizability is unclear: all women were mothers. 2. Did not control specifically for physical limitations. 3. Control for psychological distress was not expansive. 4. Other unidentified characteristics. 5. Cannot determine the direction of the relationships.

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		Engagement); age, early health, poverty and education.			4.Women with diverse and persistent CE were significantly more likely to report good physical functioning than those with persistent CE.	
Jackson & Goodman, 2011	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: SES; gender; CES-D.	1,263 participants, black or white race/ethnicity (both non-Hispanic), in 7–12th grade.	Examine the social patterning of depressive symptoms in adolescence, using SES, gender and race/ethnicity.	1.For each of the three social status domains, as predicted, the relatively lower status group evidenced higher depressive symptoms. 2.Female and black participants reported more depressive symptoms than their male and white counterparts. Black race/ethnicity did not predict greater depressive symptoms when SES was taken into account, but the female gender did.	1.Race/ethnicity was based on school records and SES on parent reports. 2.Not representative of teenagers not enrolled at school. Fewer black participants.
Ochieng, 2011	United Kingdom	Community-based qualitative study.	10 African-Caribbean households comprising 24 adolescents (12–18 years of age) and 18 adults (22–60 years of age).	Explore the effects of kin, social network and the neighbourhood on an individual's well-being.	1.Kin networks continue to benefit individuals. 2.Well-being is partly determined by the links individuals have with their families; consequently; health and social care practitioners need to take into account the various characteristics of an individual's social network and local neighborhood in order to plan effective health promotion strategies. 3.In considering new ways to promote wellbeing, practitioners need to incorporate ways to promote social support and community wellbeing models that incorporate the family and community strengths.	Based on a small sample of purposively selected participants.
Priest, Baxter & Hayes, 2011	Australia	Longitudinal quantitative study: Strengths	4,735 children (4% Indigenous).	1.Analyze living environments. 2.Examine social	1.Significant differences in family and neighbourhood characteristics were found between those from Indigenous	1.Bias in data analysis.

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		and Difficulties Questionnaire (child's mental health); family structure, housing conditions, income, parenting practices, social capital, support, neighbourhood safety.		and emotional outcomes.	backgrounds compared to the reference group: Indigenous reported lower parental income, lower level of mother's education, mother with low consistent parenting and living in unsafe neighbourhoods. 2.Significant differences in SDQ-total difficulties were found for children with an Indigenous mother, even when controlling for family and neighbourhood characteristics. 3.Significant differences in child mental-health outcomes were found for all SDQ-subcales for children with Indigenous mothers.	2.No consensus on classifying ethnic groups.
Sternthal, Slopen & Williams, 2011	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: measures such as Race, Stress (acute life event, financial employment, relationship, early life, community stressors); Everyday Discrimination Scale; Perceived Racism Scale; CES-D; self-reported health.	1,240 non-Hispanic Blacks, 983 non-Hispanic Whites, 802 Hispanics, and 80 of other racial groups.	Address three limitations of prior research on the association between stress and health: the assessment of stressors, examine individual stressors and adjust for SES.	1.Significant racial differences in both the levels and clustering of stressors. Blacks exhibited a higher prevalence of stress overall, and compared to Whites, multiple stressors were more common among AAs reporting any stressors. 2.The associations between stressors and health were remarkably consistent across racial groups. 3.The greater clustering of stressors and the higher rates of relationship and financial stressors among Blacks and American-born Hispanics suggest that these stressors may be especially important factors in understanding minorities' relatively worse health profiles.	1.Because of the cross-sectional method, it's impossible to establish temporal order among the variables. 2.Lacking measures of acculturation stress; other types of stressors were overlooked.
Walsemann, Bell & Goosby, 2011	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: CES-D; high school racial composition by	10,350 respondents enrolled in 80 high schools: 5,561 whites, 2,030 blacks, 1,834 Hispanics, 738	1.Investigate the effect of high school racial composition on	1.As the percentage of whites increased, blacks reported more depressive symptoms. Asian and Hispanic respondents who attended white high schools had lower depressive symptoms	1.Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 2.Results not generalizable (high

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		percentage of non-Hispanic white students; family structure, perceived discrimination, school attachment, family SES; school SES.	Asians and 187 of other race.	depressive symptoms from adolescence to early adulthood. 2.Explore if that association varies by race/ethnicity and adult SES.	than those attending minority schools, but they also experienced a slower decline in depressive symptoms through early adulthood. Adult SES mediated the relationship between high school racial composition and depressive symptoms for black, but not for Asian or Hispanic. 2.Results suggest that high school racial composition is associated with trajectories of depressive symptoms through early adulthood, but the effect differs by respondents' race/ethnicity. Racial/ethnic disparities in depressive symptoms during early adulthood may have their origins in adolescence.	school environment in 1994/95). 3.Depressive symptoms are not representative of all mental health issues.
Walsemann, Bell & Maitra, 2011	United States	Cross sectional quantitative study: CES-D; somatic symptoms; school racial composition (% whites); family structure, perceived discrimination, school attachment, school and family SES.	18,419 students attending high schools in 1994/5: 9,743 whites, 3,909 non-Hispanic blacks, 3,127 Hispanics, 1,286 Asian/Pacific Islanders, 148 American Indians, and 206 of other race/ethnicity.	1.Measure how school-level racial composition affects depressive and somatic symptoms. 2.Explore if the association differs by race/ethnicity.	1.Black students experienced more depressive symptoms and were at greater risk of experiencing high somatic symptoms when attending white schools than when attending minority schools. School-level SES did not mediate this relationship. 3.Students' perceptions of discrimination and school attachment attenuated the interactive associations between race (black vs white) % white students at school, and depressive and somatic symptoms.	1.Representative only of students who were enrolled in junior/senior high school in 94/95. 2. Using cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences. 3.Depressive and somatic symptoms constitute only two dimensions of health
Albright & LaFromboise, 2010	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study:	114 American Indian middle-school (fifth, sixth, and seventh grades) students who	Examine if American Indian adolescents who indicated an Indian	1.No associations between the baseline cultural identification scales and longitudinal change in hopelessness.	1.Small number of participants. 2.Inconsistent with other studies.

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		Cultural identification Scale; Likert scales; Hopelessness Scale for Children.	were living on a single reservation in the Northern Plains area of the United States	cultural identification would also indicate less hopelessness.	2.Indian identification was not associated with hopelessness at either time point. 3.The association between White identification and hopelessness was significant and negative, and no significant associations with hopelessness were found for Indian or bicultural identification.	3.Intracommunity dynamics were not taken into account.
Carrasco-Garrido, De Andrés, Hernández Barrera, Jiménez-Trujillo & Jiménez-García, 2010	Spain	Cross-sectional quantitative study, data from the National Health Survey in Spain.	1,581 spanish women (527 Roma).	Describe the health status of Roma women in Spain.	1. Roma women are more likely to suffer from certain health problems such as obesity, depression or migraines. 2. In terms of lifestyles, Roma women report significantly higher levels of alcohol consumption than non-Roma women and do less physical exercise, although they smoke less. 3. Roma women have a poorer perception of their health, but the percentage of women who attend health services is not significantly higher. Roma consume less medication but self-medicate more.	1.Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 2.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis.
Franco, 2010	United States	Longitudinal quantitative study: Interval response scale; Parenting Stress Index; Neighborhood Social Disorder and Social Cohesion scale; social support, child's health and temperament,	2,865 mothers: 48% non-Hispanic Black, 26% Hispanic, 23% non-Hispanic White, 3% other ethnicity.	Study the effects of neighborhood-level factors on parenting stress in the first 3 years of parenthood.	1.Parental stress is significantly greater in neighborhoods with higher levels of social disorder and lower levels of social cohesion. 2.Mothers who were depressed, younger, were exposed to violence, had less than a high school education, were unemployed, were uninvolved with the child's father, had poorer health, had less social support, never attended religious services, and had children with poorer health and difficult temperament experienced the highest levels of parenting stress.	1.Other important variables have not been included in the analysis. 2.No differences in mean levels of parenting stress or social cohesion, though the analytic sample had higher mean scores on social disorder (vs control).

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		religion, depression, violence.			3. Non-Hispanic Blacks, Hispanics, and those in the Other Race–Ethnicity category showed higher levels of parenting stress than non-Hispanic Whites.	3.Regression analyses may not take into account potential clustering of data.
Fuligni, 2010	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: self-reported checklist (family interactions, other daily activities); Profile of Moods States.	220 young adults; 55 Latino, 39 East Asian, 67 Filipino, 59 European backgrounds.	Explore ethnic differences in interactions with parents and siblings, the role of other activities in family interactions, and the association of family interactions with psychological distress and wellbeing.	1.Young adults reported spending comparatively less time in family interactions than in other activities. The total amount of time that young adults spent doing things either with, or for, their parents and siblings was not insignificant. Parents and siblings remain an important part of the daily lives of individuals as they move into their mid-twenties. 2.Ethnic differences emerged in only two aspects of family interactions: Filipino reported the greatest amount of time spent helping the family and the lowest frequency of conflict with parents and siblings; Latin American did not spend more time helping the family on a daily basis than those from European and East Asian backgrounds. 3.Spending more leisure time with parents and siblings was associated with higher levels of happiness and lower levels of distress at the daily level. Family conflict occurred at a very low frequency and was particularly significant for distress and wellbeing. There is a tendency for family interactions (leisure time, conflict) to be more consequential for psychological distress and wellbeing among Filipino.	1.Small sample for each group. 2.Self-report may not be the best method to assess. 3.Direction of causality could not be definitively determined.

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Herrera et al., 2010	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Cognitive Assessment Screening Test (global cognitive functioning); CES-D; self-report of leisure activities.	113 Latino and 113 Caucasian post-menopausal women.	1. Identify differences in the frequency of engagement in leisure activities. 2. Determine relations between leisure activities, depression and cognitive functioning.	1. Latino women had significantly higher levels of depressive symptom burden compared to Caucasian women. No significant difference between cognitive functioning or physical health were observed. 2. Greater participation in organized social activities was significantly associated with lower levels of depressive symptom burden for both Latino and Caucasian. Latinas are more likely than Caucasian women to care for elderly or disabled relatives.	1. Using self-reported measures may be a cause of bias. 2. Participants were English-speaking women. 3. Latina ethnicity was used as a heterogeneous group.
Seaton, Caldwell, Sellers & Jackson, 2010	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: Everyday Discrimination Scale; Discrimination Attribution; CES-D; RSES; General Life Satisfaction.	1700 youths aged 13-17: 810 AA and 360 CB., and an equal gender distribution for young black AA and CB.	Examine the role of discrimination in the psychological well-being of black adolescents.	1. The present study indicate that race/ethnicity is the most frequent attribution for perceived discrimination among AA and CB youth. 2. Many Black youth attribute discriminatory incidents to characteristics other than race/ethnicity, namely physical appearance. 3. The finding that age is a reason for perceptions of discrimination is consistent with prior research indicating that approximately 15% of AA youth attribute perceived discrimination to age. 4. The results suggest no ethnic, gender or age differences in discrimination attributions. Regardless of demographic characteristics, incidents that are perceived as discriminatory are consistently perceived as such regardless of whom the target is.	1. The cross-sectional nature of the study prevents the inference of causality. 2. The instrument of this study uses an annual time period. 3. The use of an attribution for general perceptions of discriminatory incidents during the specified time period can be problematic.

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Seaton, Caldwell, Sellers & Jackson, 2010	United States	Cross-sectional quantitative study: age, gender, ethnicity; Everyday Discrimination Scale; CES-D; RSES; General Life Satisfaction.	810 AA and 360 CB youth.	Assess whether demographic constructs moderate the relationship between perceptions of discrimination and psychological wellbeing among Black youth.	<p>1.Males and older adolescents perceived more discrimination and had lower life satisfaction.</p> <p>2.Perceptions of discrimination were linked to depressive symptoms, self-esteem and life satisfaction. Depressive symptoms were negatively linked to self-esteem and life satisfaction. Self-esteem and life satisfaction were positively associated.</p> <p>3.Older AA and CB females reported higher levels of depressive symptoms than older AA males. Older CB females reported higher levels of depressive symptoms in compared to older AA males. CB females reported lower self-esteem levels than AA males when perceiving high levels of discrimination. AA females had lower life satisfaction levels than AA males, and older youth had lower life satisfaction.</p> <p>Older CB females reported lower levels of life satisfaction than older AA males in the context of high discrimination levels.</p>	<p>1.Cross-sectional data complicates causal inferences.</p> <p>2.Small effect size.</p> <p>3.Measurement of perceived discrimination could be biased.</p>
Van Cleemput, 2010	United Kingdom	Cross-sectional qualitative study: structured interviews about their beliefs, attitudes and experiences regarding access and use of health services..	27 gypsies and travellers.	Explore the long-term impact on health of processes of historical exclusion.	<p>1.Despite reporting multiple health problems, Roma travellers did not consider themselves to have poor health. However, they report, for example, suffering depression conditions which they prefer to face alone rather than receiving medical assistance.</p> <p>2. Their experience with racism in society has significant adverse effects on the mental health of these communities, fueling the general distrust towards all</p>	None mentioned.

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					sectors of the population, especially towards health professionals: the interviewees highlight the cultural insensitivity of these professionals.	
